

FINAL STUDY REPORT

Research Study on Existing Innovative Assistive Technology and Universal Design for Learning (UDL) Based Materials Facilitating Access to Learning Targeting Learners with Disabilities in Rwanda

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Research Study on Existing Innovative Assistive Technology and UDL-based Materials in Rwanda

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Abbreviations

BLF	Building Learning Foundations
CAST	Centre for Applied Special Technology
CBC	Competency Based Curriculum
CPD	Continuous Professional Development
CSO	Civil Society Organisation
CRPD	Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities
CTLRD	Curriculum, Teaching and Learning Resources Department
DEO	District Education Officer
ESSP	Education Sector Strategic Plan
FGD	Focus Group Discussion
GBV	Gender-Based Violence
GoR	Government of Rwanda
IEI	Inclusive Education Initiative
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
INGO	International Non-Governmental Organisation
KIE	Kigali Institute of Education

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KII	Key Informant Interview
MINEDUC	Ministry of Education
MINALOC	Ministry of Local Government
NCPD	National Council of Persons with Disabilities
NUDOR	National Union of Disability Organisations of Rwanda
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
OLPC	One Laptop Per Child
REB	Rwanda Basic Education Board
RSL	Rwandan Sign Language
RUB	Rwanda Union of the Blind
SNIE	Special Needs and Inclusive Education
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
UNICEF	The United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund
UDL	Universal Design for Learning
UR	University of Rwanda

1. Acknowledgements

The World Bank Inclusive Education Initiative would like to acknowledge the participation and support of the Government of Rwanda, local authorities, stakeholders, partners in education, Rwandan organizations of persons with disabilities, teachers, parents and learners with disabilities in the development of this research study. Senior management and technical staff from the Ministry of Education (MINEDUC) and Rwanda Basic Education Board (REB) provided vital information and guidance in the identification of existing efforts and strengths, weaknesses and gaps in inclusive education; the availability of assistive technology, and its use in improving learning outcomes for learners with disabilities. District Education Officers (DEO) in charge of nursery, primary and libraries, technical staff from the National Council of Persons with Disabilities (NCPD) and representatives from organizations of persons with disabilities (OPD) participated in the interview process, providing their perceptions of the current progress in supporting education for learners with disabilities and recommendations to improve the availability of assistive technology and UDL-based materials. Key development partners and private sector actors contributed by providing feedback and recommendations on collaborative ways to improve inclusive education and learning outcomes for learners with disabilities. These stakeholders included the University of Rwanda College of Education, the USAID Homes and Communities activity, Humanity & Inclusion, Save the Children, Rwanda Assistive Technology Access and Seeing Hands among others.

Very special thanks go to special schools, inclusive schools and mainstream schools, headteachers, teachers, community librarians, parents and learners with disabilities for sharing their teaching and learning experiences, the challenges they face and initiatives to support the learning journey of children with disabilities. In particular, we appreciate the contributions of Rwanda Union of the Blind (RUB) and eKitabu, who conducted the study and consolidated all findings in this report.

Thank you to all who supported this study, and we offer our appreciation in advance for your continued support for inclusive education and learners with disabilities in Rwanda.

2. Executive Summary

This study on the availability and utilization of assistive technology and Universal Design for Learning (UDL) based materials to improve the learning outcomes of learners with disabilities in Rwanda was commissioned by the World Bank's Inclusive Education Initiative (IEI). The research detailed in this report provides an overview of available assistive technology, its utilization and efficacy. The report recommends actions needed to improve the availability of assistive technology and UDL-based materials for learners with disabilities. The study ran from September 2022 to February 2023.

This evaluation report highlights findings that respond to the following research questions:

1. What assistive technologies and UDL-based materials are available in Rwanda at primary school and community levels to support learners with disabilities? Are available technologies being used and being used effectively?
2. What training and support have teachers received on inclusive education, the use of assistive technology, and the use of UDL-based materials?
3. What challenges and barriers exist that affect the availability and the effective use of assistive technology and UDL-based materials for learners with disabilities?

The researchers drew on both existing literature and primary data collected through key informant interviews (KII) and focus group discussions (FGD) with government officials, education stakeholders, organizations of persons with disabilities (OPD), DEOs in charge of nursery, primary and adult education, resource centre directors, librarians, parents, headteachers, teachers, and learners with disabilities in primary schools. A total of 291 respondents were interviewed, 141 female and 150 male, from 19 districts of Rwanda. 78 respondents had different disabilities including blindness, deafness, physical disabilities, intellectual disabilities and speech disabilities. 18 schools were visited for the research based on the number of children with disabilities they accommodate: 7 special schools, 7 inclusive model schools, and 4 mainstream schools.

The study highlighted that assistive technology and UDL-based materials for learners with disabilities in primary level in Rwanda were insufficient. Further, the UDL-based materials that are available do not fully represent UDL guidelines. Few

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assistive technologies, both low tech and high-tech, were available for learners with visual, hearing, physical or intellectual disabilities. The majority of assistive technologies available in Rwanda at this time are designed for learners who are blind or have low vision. Such technologies include screen reader software, text-to-speech software, magnification software, braille printers, Victor Readers and Orbit Reader 20 refreshable braille displays. To reflect the perceptions of respondents in the study and the ways they actually talked about assistive technologies in use in Rwandan schools, the researchers categorized all such “digital” devices that typically integrate software and hardware as “high-tech.” Traditional “analog” solutions such as Perkins brailers, the slate and stylus and braille boards were generally considered “low tech” by participants in the study. Special schools had the most assistive technologies; fewer were in inclusive model schools; and none were observed in mainstream schools. Outside of schools, specifically in community libraries visited, there were minimal assistive technologies available and those available were not being used to support learners with disabilities due to the limited knowledge of librarians.

Utilization of assistive technology by learners with disabilities mainly occurs in reading and writing, including note-taking. Respondents perceived assistive technology as effective in facilitating access to learning content, enabling learners with disabilities to participate in lessons, assessments and exams and lowering barriers to digital learning. However, the capacity and skills of teachers greatly affects utilization of assistive technology.

Teachers who received training in inclusive education and utilization of assistive technology and UDL-based materials were able to incorporate utilization in class activities, while those with no training did not use assistive technology in the classroom. The term UDL-based materials was not well understood by respondents; however, some teachers observed in the study did exhibit homegrown classroom practices that reflected UDL principles in terms of engagement, representation, action and expression. Another factor that affected utilization was limited knowledge of available assistive technology and UDL-based materials. In addition, insufficient teaching and learning materials in accessible formats limited effective utilization of devices.

The study recommends actions by government institutions, stakeholders, parents and communities. Advocacy and capacity building are both necessary to build awareness of assistive technologies and how to use them. Specifically, MINEDUC and REB need to promote the use of assistive technology and avail accessible UDL-based materials and encourage their effective use in schools in order to support learners with disabilities. Furthermore, NCPD should collaborate with Rwanda Revenue Authority to ensure that tax exemptions for assistive devices in education are clear and easy to access in order to reduce costs. Finally, the Government of Rwanda in collaboration with local and international

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partners should expedite the implementation of the Marrakesh Treaty roadmap to facilitate the production of accessible learning materials for learners with print disabilities.

This "Research Study on Existing Innovative Assistive Technology and Universal Design for Learning (UDL) Based Materials Facilitating Access to Learning Targeting Learners with Disabilities in Rwanda" advances progress in realizing inclusive and equitable quality education. It will inform key stakeholders in relation to past, present and future education interventions, in particular to prioritize provision and utilization of teaching and learning resources that are accessible for all learners with and without disabilities, leaving no one behind.

3. Introduction

This report focuses on the availability and utilization of assistive technology and UDL-based materials in and out of schools to improve learning outcomes for learners with disabilities. The study also assessed the efficacy of assistive technology and UDL-based materials and the challenges that hinder effective utilization. Data that informed this report was gathered from KIIs and FGDs, as well as through site observations. The researchers involved learners with and without disabilities in primary schools from mainstream, inclusive and special schools, their teachers, headteachers, community librarians, parents of children with disabilities, resource centre administrators, OPD representatives, government officials and other education stakeholders.

The objectives of the research were to identify, analyze, and assess the availability and utilization of innovative assistive technology and UDL-based accessible digital multimedia materials facilitating access to learning and teaching resources for learners with disabilities in Rwanda.

The next two sections of the report highlight the background and context of inclusive education in Rwanda and the availability of assistive technology and UDL-based materials. The section on methodology outlines the tools used to collect and analyze the data, as well as the limitations of this study. Section six presents the detailed findings of the study, followed by a section on the analysis of data collected to answer the research questions. The final section elaborates recommendations for stakeholders in inclusive education and major conclusions of the study.

4. Background and Literature Review

Assistive technology has been shown to be effective in enhancing the learning experiences of learners with disabilities. In a study by Burgstahler and Cory (2008), the authors found that assistive technology interventions were effective in improving academic performance, social interactions, and self-esteem of learners with disabilities. Furthermore, assistive technology interventions were also shown to increase the independence of learners with disabilities in academic and non-academic settings.¹ In addition to improving academic outcomes, assistive technology interventions have also been shown to promote inclusion and reduce stigmatization of learners with disabilities. In a study by Sainato and Goldstein (1993), the authors found that the use of assistive technology interventions improved the social acceptance of learners with disabilities by their peers.

Several studies have shown the effectiveness of UDL-based materials in improving academic outcomes for learners with disabilities. In a study by Rose and Meyer (2002), the authors found that the use of UDL-based materials improved the reading comprehension of middle school learners with disabilities. Similarly, in a study by Edyburn (2010), the author found that the use of UDL-based materials improved the math problem-solving abilities of learners with disabilities. UDL-based materials have also been shown to increase learner engagement and motivation. In a study by Dalton and Pisha (2014), the authors found that the use of UDL-based materials improved learner engagement and motivation in high school learners with disabilities. For instance, Patton and Roschelle (2008) argue that digital textbooks offer a better alternative than traditional textbooks because they can provide instant feedback, interactive representations, and the system of universal design for learning (UDL).

Assistive technology can provide learners with disabilities with the necessary tools to access information and complete tasks, while UDL-based materials can provide all learners with the opportunity to access educational materials that are accessible and engaging.

¹ Cawthon and Garberoglio, Bridging the communication divide, Language, Learning and Technology, 2014

4.1. Inclusive and Special Needs Education Context of Rwanda

The GoR has made efforts to improve special needs education. It has set forth the National Policy on Disability (2013) that recognizes the right of persons with disabilities to access quality education and provides for the inclusion of learners with disabilities in mainstream schools. The policy aligns with United Nations Sustainable Development Goal Four: “ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all.”

Other accomplishments include ratifying the United Nations’ Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD), setting forth the [National Policy of Persons with Disabilities and Four Year Strategic Plan \(2021-2024\)](#) and the [Special Needs and Inclusive Education Policy \(2018\)](#) which are committed to increasing the number of children with disabilities enrolled in school—with provision of reasonable accommodations.

According to the 2012 Rwanda population census, 1.7% of children under 17 were persons with disabilities. Furthermore, the Rwanda school census of 2014 indicates that only 24,862 children with disabilities were enrolled in pre-school, primary, and lower secondary schools, representing just 0.5% of the population under 17. This number is low in light of the fact that globally, persons with disabilities represent 10% to 15% of any human population. These figures suggest that many children with disabilities are not attending school, and also that children who have not been screened for disabilities are not receiving support in schools according to their needs. The World Health Organization acknowledged these low figures, suggesting that although there has been an increase in the number of children with disabilities attending school, the change has not been widespread, and many challenges persist.²

According to Rwanda’s Statistical Yearbook 2020/2021, there are a total of 3,691 primary schools in Rwanda. However, the number of schools that can accommodate the needs of learners with disabilities with some form of specialized support, which includes 50 special schools and 60 inclusive model schools, accounts for less than 3% of total primary schools. The National Council of Persons with Disabilities (NCPD) reports³ that there are 50 special schools in Rwanda that cater to the needs of learners with disabilities, and 60 inclusive model schools supported by Humanity & Inclusion, UNICEF and the Ministry of Education, two per district. These schools and centres enroll learners with disabilities, they

² World Health Organization World Report on Disability, 2011.

³ National Council of Persons with Disabilities Annual Report, 2012.

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have infrastructure and materials adapted for learners with special needs, and they have teachers and staff trained in special needs education.

By policy, schools are expected to accommodate the learning needs of all learners. However, special schools accommodate the specific educational needs of children with disabilities, such as provision of adapted teaching and learning materials, availability of assistive technology, and the support of specialist teachers trained in special needs and inclusive education. In general, teachers of learners with disabilities, including deaf learners and learners with intellectual disabilities, face the challenge that there is currently no curriculum designed or adapted for learners with special needs or disabilities, as noted by the Ministry of Education and UNICEF in their 2016 report on children with disabilities and their right to education.⁴ A further challenge in relation to special schools is the cost of enrollment: the majority of special schools in Rwanda are either private, founded and funded by religious organizations, or government-aided and are boarding in nature, which incurs additional fees and makes special schools expensive.

The table in Annex A enumerates the special schools and inclusive model schools. The table below from Rwanda's Statistical Yearbook 2020/21 enumerates the numbers of schools with and without physical infrastructure adapted for learners with physical disabilities, such as ramps and accessible toilets.

Table 1. Primary schools with infrastructure adapted for learners with disabilities in Rwanda (Statistical Year Book 2020/21)

Availability of infrastructure adapted for learners with disabilities	# in 2021
Primary schools with adapted infrastructure	1,390
Primary schools without adapted infrastructure	2,301

⁴ Ministry of Education, UNICEF, Education Development Trust, A study on children with disabilities and their right to Education in Rwanda, 2016, pg 21.

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In addition, the Statistical Yearbook 2020/21 indicates that there are approximately 23,000 learners with disabilities in primary schools, disaggregated by disability in the table below.

Table 2. Numbers of learners with disabilities in Rwanda disaggregated by disability

Type of disability	Male	Female	Total
Physical or motor disabilities	3,921	2,959	6,880
Specific learning disabilities	3,863	3,058	6,921
Visual impairments	1,467	1,222	2,689
Hearing impairments	809	754	1,563
Developmental disabilities	758	718	1,476
Speech disabilities	1,284	866	2,150
Multiple disabilities	925	823	1,748
Total	13,027	10,400	23,427

The Statistical Yearbook 2020/21 further states that 10.2% of total teachers have been trained in special needs and inclusive education.⁵

⁵ Republic of Rwanda, Ministry of Education, 2020/21 Educational Statistical Yearbook, February 2022, p.85.

4.2. Availability and efficacy of assistive technologies and UDL-based materials

Rwanda's ICT in Education Policy 2016 aims to increase access to education at all levels, improve education and training quality, and strengthen education and training relevance to the employment market, including the incorporation of 21st-century skills.⁶

The Rwandan government has taken steps to widen the availability and use of assistive technology. For example, in April 2022, REB endorsed the Orbit Reader 20 refreshable braille display in a countrywide launch to support learners who are blind. In 2021 and 2022, RUB and eKitabu distributed Orbit Readers, tablets and computers with accessible content to support learners who are blind or have low vision and their teachers. Rwanda Revenue Authority also offers tax exemptions for educational materials such as assistive technologies used by learners with disabilities in primary education.⁷

Although Rwanda has implemented a number of ICT initiatives in education through various programs and partnerships, these devices are in general not accessible for learners with disabilities. For example, in primary education, beginning in 2008, Rwanda's "One Laptop Per Child" project distributed 278,975 XO laptops to schools countrywide; however, these devices lacked assistive features, some of which are now integrated in newer computers. The table below shows various digital devices deployed in Rwandan schools (compiled by eKitabu in collaboration with stakeholders in the Special Needs and Inclusive Education Technical Working Group, 2022).

Table 3. Numbers of devices distributed in schools

Location	Schools	Laptops	XO OLPC	Tablets	Projectors	Orbit Reader
East	215	15,385	60,809	109	293	27
West	374	20,103	68,855	22	377	8
North	264	15,245	52,214	2,733	290	18

⁶ Ministry of Education, ICT in Education Policy, 2016.

⁷ Institute of Certified Public Accountants of Rwanda, CPA F2.4 Taxation Study Manual, Second Edition 2020, p. 94.

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Location	Schools	Laptops	XO OLPC	Tablets	Projectors	Orbit Reader
South	300	21,181	68,831	19	414	22
Kigali	54	4,604	19,266	1,143	89	4
Total	1,207	76,518	269,975	4,026	1,463	79

Assistive technology is defined as technology that increases, improves, or maintains the functional abilities of persons with disabilities.⁸ Recent studies have investigated the efficacy of assistive technology in primary and secondary schools for children with disabilities. The studies have found that the use of assistive technology can have a positive impact in overcoming reading difficulties in learners with disabilities. Sakalli Demirok et al. (2019) found that technological enrichment of the learning environment helps teachers motivate their learners.⁹ Additionally, assistive technologies can improve the reading and comprehension skills of learners with disabilities. Similarly, Niyigena et al. (2021) found that the use of screen readers and braille devices in secondary schools improved the reading and writing abilities of learners with visual impairments.¹⁰

Research on the use of assistive technology in Rwanda has highlighted the need for more appropriate and accessible assistive technology for persons with disabilities. According to the World Bank's study "*Understanding multidimensional determinants of disability-inclusive education*" (2022), both the National Union of Disability Organizations in Rwanda (NUDOR) and NCPD noted that assistive devices were only available to about twenty percent of the children in special schools. In general, where devices were available, the utilization was minimal due to limited capacity of teachers in how to

⁸ Rose, D., Hasselbring, T.S., Stahl, S., & Zabala, J. (2005). Assistive Technology and Universal Design for Learning: Two Sides of the Same Coin, p. 509.

⁹ Sakalli Demirok, M., Gunduz, N., A. Yergazina, A., A. Maydangalieva, Z., & L. Ryazanova, E. (2019). Determining the Opinions of Special Education Teachers Regarding the Use of Assistive Technologies for Overcoming Reading Difficulties. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (iJET)*, 14(22), pp. 141–153. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v14i22.11761>

¹⁰ Niyigena, E., Nsengiyumva, J., & Kamanzi, P. (2021). Assistive technology for learners with visual impairments in secondary schools in Rwanda. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning*, 16(5), 66-74.

use them.¹¹ A study by Niyonsaba et al. (2019) found that the assistive technology available in Rwanda is imported and not well-suited to the needs of the local population. The study also identified a lack of trained personnel to support the use of assistive technology. A study by Niyigena et al. (2020) found that while some schools in Rwanda have started to incorporate assistive technology and UDL into their curriculum, educators lack awareness and understanding of the potential benefits. The study also highlighted the need for more training and resources for educators to effectively utilize assistive technology and apply UDL in their classrooms.¹²

A range of assistive technology and services still needs to be developed and procured for schools for learners with special educational needs. Evidence from special schools for learners with visual impairments, for example, confirms that REB has continuously procured educational materials for sighted learners for the school, even with repeated requests from the school for appropriate alternatives that could include audio, braille or other tactile materials. Rwandan schools for learners with hearing impairments continue to use different modes of communication in teaching and learning because standards for instruction in Rwandan Sign Language in schools are not yet in place. Schools for learners with learning disabilities continue to request curriculum materials and appropriate programs to cater for the needs of their learners. In all cases however, the situation of learners with disabilities in mainstream schools and inclusive model schools as well as the situation of learners in special schools remains challenging for teachers as they are required to adhere to the same assessment standards, yet they do not have appropriate instructional resources, services and approaches (MINEDUC, 2018).

4.3. Availability and effective use of UDL-based materials

Universal Design for Learning (UDL) is a framework that supports the development of flexible learning materials and environments that can accommodate the needs of learners with diverse abilities and learning styles.

A focus on UDL cannot be independent of the use of assistive technology, as both approaches build on effective utilization

¹¹ World Bank. (2022). *Understanding Multidimensional Determinants of Disability-Inclusive Education: Lessons from Rwanda, Sierra Leone, and Zambia*.

¹² Niyigena, E., Nsengiyumva, J., & Kamanzi, P. (2021). Assistive technology for learners with visual impairments in secondary schools in Rwanda. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning*, 16(5), 66-74.

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of accessible learning materials.¹³ UDL, pioneered by the Centre for Applied Special Technologies ([CAST.org](https://udlguidelines.cast.org)), is an approach to curriculum design and teaching methods that aims to make education more inclusive and accessible for all learners according to their abilities, disabilities, needs and learning styles. UDL guidelines inform the design of lessons and learning environments to reduce barriers in education and give all learners the opportunity to become purposeful, motivated, resourceful, knowledgeable, strategic and goal-directed. UDL principles allow for a holistic approach to education for all learners, including those that are often marginalized, especially learners with disabilities.¹⁴ In practical terms, providing instructional materials in multiple formats can help learners with disabilities access information and engage with learning content. This can include videos, audio recordings, graphics and text.

In Rwanda, recent studies have investigated the integration of UDL principles and practices in primary and secondary school curricula. The studies have found that the use of UDL-based materials can have a positive impact on learning outcomes of all learners. Twagirayezu et al. (2020) found that the use of UDL-based materials in primary schools improved the learning outcomes of all learners, including learners with disabilities.¹⁵ Similarly, Musabende et al. (2021) found that the application of UDL principles in higher education improved learning outcomes of learners with disabilities.¹⁶ REB provides guidance and support to teachers and educators in Rwanda to develop inclusive learning environments that meet the needs of all learners. REB has developed guidelines and policies for inclusive education, which include strategies for implementation of UDL.

International development partners have made efforts to ensure the availability of accessible UDL-based materials. For example, UNICEF's Accessible Digital Textbooks for All initiative adapted a Rwandan P1 English Textbook into an accessible digital format (EPUB 3.2) applying UDL principles. The accessible digital textbook gives all learners, including learners with disabilities, access to information in multiple accessible formats such as audio narration, sign language video, audio descriptions of images and other features to suit diverse access needs, preferences and learning styles. Through these formats, printed books which were previously inaccessible can be made accessible to learners who are

¹³ Rose, D., Hasselbring, T.S., Stahl, S., & Zabala, J. (2005). Assistive Technology and Universal Design for Learning: Two Sides of the Same Coin, p. 509.

¹⁴ <https://udlguidelines.cast.org>.

¹⁵ Twagirayezu, J., Nsengiyumva, J., & Kamanzi, P. (2020). The impact of Universal Design for Learning on primary school learners' learning outcomes in Rwanda. *Journal of Educational Technology Development and Exchange*, 3(1), 1-14.

¹⁶ Musabende, P., Twagirayezu, J., & Kamanzi, P. (2021). The use of assistive technology and Universal Design for Learning in higher education in Rwanda. *Journal of Educational Technology Development and Exchange*, 4(1), 1-12.

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blind or have low vision, learners who are deaf or hard of hearing, and learners with learning, cognitive or developmental disabilities.¹⁷

Special needs and inclusive education teachers have highlighted a lack of adapted textbooks for learners with visual impairments, especially with image descriptions of diagrams and pictures.¹⁸ REB's Curriculum, Teaching and Learning Resources Department (CTLRD) is currently developing 28 accessible textbook titles for use in pre-primary and primary classrooms. Further, in collaboration with REB, actors such as FCDO's Building Learning Foundations (BLF), World Bank, USAID Soma Umenye, University of Rwanda and eKitabu have adapted learning materials and made them available on REB's e-learning platform.

¹⁷ UNICEF Accessible Digital Textbooks Using Universal for Learning, for learners with and without disabilities, 2020, pg 10.

¹⁸ Ministry of Education, UNICEF, Education Development Trust: A Study on children with disabilities and their right to education, 2016.

5. Methodological Approach

Research conducted under this component aims to gather information on available assistive technology and UDL-based materials for learners with disabilities and how they are being utilized to facilitate inclusion within and outside the classroom. The study applies an approach and methodology that are participatory in nature and involve multiple partners across different phases.

Overall, the study focuses on reach, utilization, and impact on learning outcomes. Through data collection and analysis, this study provides an evidence-based report on the availability and utilization of assistive technology and UDL-based materials designed to foster learning competencies, independence, and skill-building in an inclusive manner. Furthermore, the study highlights gaps and makes specific recommendations to improve access for learners with disabilities.

Outputs are:

- Evaluate the availability and efficacy of assistive technology in facilitating learning in and out of the classroom;
- Assess the availability and utilization of open-source UDL-based materials facilitating learning in and out of the classroom;
- Sample users of assistive technology and UDL-based materials and understand the dimensions of assistive technology access and the use of those materials in delivering quality education;
- Convene a consultative workshop to guide the study;
- Compile and curate relevant training content building on the use of existing assistive technologies and UDL-based materials in consultation with teachers, targeting learners with disabilities;
- Conduct Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) on training modules, the uptake of assistive technology, and the use of training materials in libraries and schools at the primary level; and
- Compile and present findings and recommendations, and organize a conference for learning and dissemination purposes to promote adoption.

5.1. Research methods

The methodological approach used for the entire research is qualitative in nature, to enable the collection of in-depth information, views, and opinions of a range of respondents on their experiences on the use of assistive technology and UDL-based materials.

Research instruments for data collection were developed after a thorough review of materials and consultative discussions among the research team members. The following instruments were developed and used:

- KII guides (semi-structured interviews);
- Focus Group Discussion (FGDs) guides; and
- A school observation guide.

The research instruments were developed in English and Kinyarwanda and were reviewed by the World Bank IEI team before being used. The instruments were made available in accessible formats for enumerators with visual disabilities. Data collection guides are attached as [Annex B](#).

5.2. Research design

5.2.1. Desk review

In order to achieve the overall objective of the study, a literature review was conducted. It involved:

- Analysis of existing reports and studies about inclusive education in Rwanda;
- Analysis of existing reports about assistive technology and UDL-based materials in primary schools; and
- Analysis of existing legal instruments and policies regarding inclusive education and ICT in education.

The documents included in the literature review involved a desk review of key documents such as:

- Rwanda Special Needs and Inclusive Education Policy (2018)
- Rwanda ICT in Education Policy (2016)

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- Education for All Plan of Action (2003)
- Statistical Yearbook 2020/2021 from MINEDUC
- World Bank IEI, A Landscape Review of ICT for Disability-Inclusive Education (2022)
- National Policy for Persons with Disabilities Strategic Plan (2021-2024)
- UNICEF & Education Development Trust, A study on children with disabilities and their right to Education, Rwanda (2016)
- UNICEF Accessible Digital Textbooks Using Universal Design for Learning for Learners With and Without Disabilities
- National Council for Persons with Disabilities Annual Report (2012)
- Stakeholder reports such as Uburezi Iwacu Gender Equality and Social Inclusion Desk Review Report (2022)
- Other research documentation on similar topics

5.2.2. Training of enumerators

In total, eight enumerators from the research team were trained on how to use the data collection tools. The characteristics of the group of enumerators includes:

- The team is composed of persons with and without disabilities;
- Team members are fluent in the following: English, Kinyarwanda, RSL, and braille;
- Team members have skills and experience critical to high quality data collection.

The enumerators were trained for two days on the data collection instruments and research principles and approaches. Key areas of focus were acquiring informed consent from respondents, recording answers into audio or written form, data transfer to central storage, and transcription. Furthermore, the enumerators reviewed the instruments, especially the English and Kinyarwanda in accessible format in order to ensure uniformity.

5.2.3. Piloting of research instruments

Instruments were piloted in 2 schools: one mainstream school (GS Kimironko II), and one special school for deaf learners (GS Institut Filippo Smaldone). Additionally, one KII was conducted with a representative from NUDOR. The main

objective of the piloting of research instruments was to ensure enumerators were well-prepared. This included familiarity with the data collection tools, ensuring that the intended information was gathered, and to assess optimal durations for the KIIs and FGDs. The pilot test was conducted with individuals similar to the targeted respondents: KIIs with headteachers and stakeholders, FGDs with teachers, FGDs with learners with disabilities, and an observation exercise on assistive technology and UDL-based materials. Data collected during the pilot test was used to revise the tools accordingly. A summary of the pilot test was submitted to the World Bank IEI team in the piloting report. Key outcomes from the pilot exercise included revision of several of the key terms used in the data collection tools, for example, the translation of key terms “assistive technology” and “Universal Design for Learning” into Kinyarwanda for respondents to understand and be able to provide direct responses.

5.2.4. Authorization from REB

The World Bank IEI team provided an introduction letter to carry out the study. This letter, along with the research approach and field schedule, was shared with REB in order to obtain the necessary authorization to access and visit schools. The authorization letter was addressed and sent to all district mayors to inform them of the research activity and for their facilitation in the research process.

5.2.5. Field scheduling and data collection

During the scheduling, the objectives of the research and its intended respondents were explained so that participants could be informed beforehand. The enumerators scheduled dates for field visits and informed the schools and key informants of the dates and times for interviews.

5.2.6. Compile and curate relevant training content

Data collection tools also focused on the availability and use of the following by teachers in schools: training content, training provided and/or training received on assistive technologies and UDL-based materials facilitating access to learning targeting learners with disabilities. The research team has begun to compile all training materials identified from REB's e-learning platform and from interviews and focus groups in which teachers mentioned that they had received relevant training under BLF or other interventions.

5.2.7. Debrief sessions

For quality assurance and ensuring that the expected information was being gathered, the enumerators, led by the field team supervisor, held debrief sessions daily. The debrief sessions covered the respondents reached, and the information gathered, especially if there was any new information the respondents wanted to discuss further. In addition, the debrief sessions covered any challenges experienced in the field and how to mitigate them moving forward. From the data collection, the challenges experienced were DEOs not being available during the agreed-upon dates and times due to other commitments. This was mitigated by rescheduling or holding the interviews virtually.

5.2.8. Data processing, management and storage

Data was recorded on recording devices and smartphones upon getting informed consent from respondents. The audio recordings were then uploaded to a Google Drive with restricted access for security storage. Photos were taken in the field after receiving signed consent forms from respondents. These photos were stored in the same Google Drive. All physical consent forms signed by respondents were collected and have been stored in a locked storage unit.

5.3. Sampling strategy

5.3.1. Selection of locations

Districts for the study were selected across the country and each province was covered. The main criteria for selection were based on the types of schools, resource centres and sites that were targeted for the study, for example, schools that include learners with disabilities. A total of 19 districts were covered in this research.

Schools were selected based on their categorization as special, inclusive or mainstream schools, while community libraries were selected based on their possession of assistive technology. A mix, reasonably representative of the Rwandan system, of special schools, inclusive model schools and mainstream schools were purposively selected across the 19 districts. In each district, schools, community libraries and resource centres as well as district offices were visited to gather information on availability and utilization of assistive technology. The table below identifies the districts and institutions within those districts visited.

Table 4. List of institutions reached by districts

Provinces	Districts	Institutions
Kigali MVK	Gasabo	GS Musave, Kigali Public Library, GS Kimironko II, Gasabo District office, MINEDUC, REB, World Vision, Save the Children, NCPD, RATA
	Kicukiro	Masaka Resource Centre, H&I, RNUD, NUDOR
	Nyarugenge	GS Institut Filippo Smaldone, GS Burema, Nyarugenge District office, RUB
North	Rulindo	GS Rukingu, Rulindo District Office,
	Gakenke	EP Gitabi, Gakenke District Office
	Musanze	Blessing School, Musanze District office
	Burera	Sunzu Yacu Community Library, Burera District Office
South	Kamonyi	GS Rosa Mystica, Kamonyi District Office
	Ruhango	Ruhango community library, Ruhango District office
	Huye	EP Bunazi, Huye District Office
	Nyaruguru	Educational institute of blind of Franciscan Sisters servants of the cross, Nyaruguru District Office
East	Rwamagana	HVP Gatagara, Rwamagana Community library, Rwamagana District Office
	Kirehe	GS Rwantonde. Kirehe District Office

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Provinces	Districts	Institutions
	Kayonza	University of Rwanda, College of Education
	Nyagatare	GS Rwisirabo, Nyagatare District office
West	Rubavu	Ubumwe Community Centre, Rubavu District Office
	Ngororero	EP Muramba A, Kabaya Community library, Ngororero District office
	Karongi	GS Gitesi, Karongi District Office
	Nyamasheke	GS Gashashi, Nyamasheke District Office

The schools sampled for the research included special schools, inclusive model schools and mainstream schools. The sampling approach was used in order to understand the similarities and differences in inclusive education and availability of assistive technology and UDL-based materials to accommodate the needs of learners with disabilities.

Figure 1. Number of schools reached

As illustrated in the figure above, the total number of schools reached was 19 schools and centres. These included seven special schools, 7 inclusive model schools, 4 mainstream schools and 1 resource centre. Special schools and inclusive schools had the majority of learners with disabilities, which explains why they constituted the largest number of schools sampled.

5.3.2. Selection of respondents

The respondents sampled for this research were purposively selected based on their experiences, roles and responsibilities in working in inclusive education and supporting learners with disabilities in improving their learning outcomes.

Respondents for the KIIs and FGDs were selected following the selection of schools, institutions and community centres. Relevant KII respondents that held information about the research topic were identified from the central level as well as interviewing the DEOs in charge of nursery, primary and adult literacy.

For the FGDs, learners with disabilities and teachers in sampled schools were selected to participate in the discussions. This was a similar approach in selecting parents of children with disabilities in the communities around the community libraries, who responded through FGDs. The respondents in each FGD were between 6 and 8 individuals.

Overview of the respondents demographics

The research study targeted 300 respondents, and a total of 291 respondents participated in the research. Of the participants, 141 were female and 150 were male, respondents were involved in the research. They included 56 KII respondents and 235 FGD respondents.

Figure 2. Demographics of respondents

Disability categorization of respondents

78 respondents who participated in this research had different types of disabilities, as elaborated in the graph below. The disability categorization was self-reported.

Figure 3. Disability disaggregates of Respondents

The majority of the respondents with disabilities were learners in the visited schools, followed by headteachers and teachers mainly from special schools.

5.4. Data analysis

The transcripts from the semi-structured interviews and the focus group discussions were analyzed using conventional qualitative methods including thematic analysis (inductive and deductive), contradictions within the narrative, and coverage. Results from different stakeholder groups were triangulated to understand and attempt to rationalize responses.

The school observation guides were evaluated using basic statistical methods (frequency, standard deviation).

Atlas.ti, an analytical software tool familiar to the research team, was used to code and analyze qualitative data relying on themes to identify patterns of responses.

5.5. Ethics

The research team introduced the study to all respondents and shared the authorization letters from REB, to gain confidence and minimize discomfort in responding to the questions. The research team also offered to show the research questions to the KII respondents in advance and to address any concerns or questions they might have. The purpose of the research was explained to all participants in advance of the discussions, including an explanation that participation was voluntary.

Consent forms were then given to respondents to sign prior to starting the interview process. The consent form included giving permission to interview the respondent, for audio recording of the interview session, and to take pictures of the process and the school. The respondent gave consent to each request prior to starting. Where an individual was not comfortable with audio recording of the session, notes were then taken. When respondents were not comfortable having their pictures taken, this option was omitted from the data collection exercise. Since the study involved the participation of young learners, the guardian, who was the headteacher, signed the consent form on behalf of the learners; however, the learners also gave verbal consent for their participation.

5.6. Limitations of the research

- **Time/duration:** The study experienced delays at the beginning of the research. The delay was due to discussions to ensure that the design would align well with the research objectives. Furthermore, there were delays based on obtaining government authorization to conduct research in schools. These delays were overcome by teaming enumerators for data collection and visiting schools in different locations at the same time.
- **Previous documentation:** The focus of the study was the availability and use of assistive technology and accessible UDL-based materials in primary education, with limited availability of relevant documentation from past interventions. The materials available only provided general information on assistive technology in education, but not at the primary level. As a result, the study relied more on government policy documents and academic articles.

6. Findings

This section presents the findings from the research conducted with government officials, stakeholders, OPDs, headteachers, teachers, learners with disabilities, librarians, and parents from 56 KIIs and 39 FGDs, with a total of 291 respondents. An in-depth analysis of the **availability**, **utilization**, and **efficacy** of assistive technology and UDL-based materials in and out of schools was conducted using the data collected.

Figure 4. Areas contributing to learning outcomes

6.1. Description of assistive technology and UDL-based materials

The respondents were asked about their understanding of assistive technology and UDL-based materials. The purpose was to gauge their knowledge, providing examples and further explanations as necessary. In addition, the research team wanted to understand if the following UDL guidelines were being applied in creating UDL-based materials to address the needs of learners with disabilities in Rwanda:

1. **Provide multiple means of engagement:** This involves designing learning experiences that are relevant, motivating and rewarding for learners with and without disabilities. In addition, multiple means of engagement can involve providing opportunities for learners to collaborate with peers and access support from teachers.
2. **Provide multiple means of representation:** This involves presenting information in multiple formats such as text, images, videos or audio to accommodate diverse learning styles, needs, abilities, disabilities and preferences. It also involves interpreting and contextualizing complex concepts using multiple means to transfer knowledge.

- 3. Provide multiple means of action & expression:** This involves providing learners with different ways to demonstrate their understanding of materials, such as through written assignments or oral presentations. It can also involve providing assistive technology such as alternative input devices to accommodate learners with print disabilities.

Through interviews and data collection, stakeholders interviewed, including government officials and OPD representatives, understood what assistive technology and UDL-based materials were. For example:

“We are exploring the use of Orbit Readers as well as other associated technologies like having large prints.”
REB official

“Depending on the settings, we have braille materials in place, and there are audiobooks as well, even though these are very limited and most of them are found in special schools and/or higher learning institutions.”
Save the Children representative

Similarly, headteachers and teachers in special schools and resource centres understood the meaning of assistive technology. However, the knowledge of teachers was mainly based on the disabilities of learners they accommodate. For example, when asked what assistive technologies were familiar to teachers in special schools for the blind, they referred to those used by blind learners:

“Yes, I know of the Orbit Reader and computers with screen readers.”
FGD with teachers from HVP Gatagara Rwamagana

Teachers and learners in inclusive model schools had limited understanding of assistive technology terminology. This was also noted in KIIs with DEOs, as some only encountered assistive technology during national exams or while inspecting special schools. On the other hand, some DEOs had knowledge of assistive technologies, especially those used by blind learners. One DEO explained:

“Blind learners are well-supported in special schools since they receive accessible materials such as books in braille format.”
DEO

Image 1. FGD with teachers from GS Rwantonde

Regarding understanding of the definition of UDL-based materials, only teachers and headteachers that had received training in UDL and inclusive education by different stakeholders were able to recognize and define relevant terms. One headteacher explained:

“We have the basic knowledge of it. Some teachers were trained in how to use [assistive devices] in their classes. However, we still lack specialization and teachers who have enough training on how to use them properly.”
KII with a headteacher

Similarly, a teacher who was trained by USAID Soma Umenye and BLF commented during an FGD:

“They trained us in how teachers must treat and take care of their learners, and how to provide lessons by giving them examples. They also included learners with disabilities, but did not go into details.”
Teacher from EP Bunazi

However, the majority of the teachers, librarians, and parents had no knowledge whatsoever of what UDL-based materials are.

6.2. Available assistive technology and UDL-based materials identified

The research aimed at investigating the availability of assistive technology and UDL-based materials in and outside of schools. This section reports the findings gathered from respondents on availability of assistive technology and UDL-based materials.

6.2.1. Assistive Technology

Respondents were asked to name examples of assistive technology they were aware of. Respondents from mainstream schools and community libraries had no knowledge of assistive technology for learners with disabilities, except for Orbit Readers which they already had. The following excerpt from an interview with a school administrator highlights this:

“Yes, [the devices] are there. For primary, they have OLPC and secondary they have laptops, but we don’t have those which can be used by children with disabilities.”

A member of the school administration, GS Burema

Image 2. Orbit Reader (left) and Perkins Braille (right) in a resource room at Blessing School for the Visually Impaired

Similarly, parents of children with disabilities had no knowledge of any assistive technology that their children can use for learning. For example, a parent in Ngororero district during an FGD said:

“We wouldn’t know about them (assistive technologies), only if we were trained about them... to know if for example your child is not moving so quickly, maybe he needs a wheelchair or crutches... so, only if you could train us on what materials we can give to our children.”

Learners and teachers in inclusive model schools had limited knowledge of assistive technologies. Some teachers identified low tech assistive technologies for learners with physical disabilities and braille papers for blind learners. For example, in an FGD with teachers in an inclusive school, they said:

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“There is a student who has a visual impairment who uses special papers to take notes, and we have another learner with a physical disability who uses a wheelchair.”

Also, interviews with DEOs in charge of nursery, primary and adult literacy had limited knowledge of types of assistive technology that can be used for learning. As one DEO explained when asked about the assistive devices they know of, they referred to basic reading, writing and communication systems:

“Children with visual impairments use braille and children with hearing impairments use sign language, and we have banners with sign language outside.”

DEO

Learners and teachers in special schools had greater knowledge of the various assistive technologies that support learners with disabilities. This knowledge of assistive technology within schools depended on the types of disabilities the school accommodated.

According to the interviews, teachers in schools understood the types of assistive technologies as either low tech or high-tech. Below are some assistive technologies highlighted in interviews and FGDs. Through observation in schools and discussions with teachers, the research team gathered information on assistive technologies that were available in schools. Some schools had resource rooms where they stored the assistive technologies, while others had “smart classrooms.” The table below presents the available assistive technologies used by learners with disabilities in the schools visited, as well as the enrollment numbers of learners with disabilities.

Table 5. Number of assistive technologies in schools visited and numbers of learners with disabilities

Schools/centres	School type	# of learners/persons with disabilities	Available assistive technology	
			High-tech	Low-tech
Masaka Resource Centre for the Blind (MRCB)	Rehabilitation centre	100 blind trainees	4 computers with JAWS screen reader 1 Victor Reader 1 Orbit Reader 20 1 Focus 1 reading camera 1 digital recorder 1 CCTV	10 Perkins braille 50 Slates and styluses
GS Musave	Inclusive model school	1 deaf learners 1 blind learner 1 low vision learner 5 intellectual disability learner 1 learner with speech disability 6 learners with physical disabilities 1 learner with multiple disability	1 Orbit Reader 20	0

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Schools/centres	School type	# of learners/persons with disabilities	Available assistive technology	
			High-tech	Low-tech
Kigali Public Library	Community library	N/A	1 Orbit Reader 20	0
GS Kimironko II	Mainstream school	2 learners with intellectual disabilities	0	0
GS Institut Filippo Smaldone	Special school	103 learners with hearing impairments	2 smart boards	0
GS Burema	Inclusive model school	1 blind, 39 with physical and intellectual disabilities	0	1 slate and stylus
GS Rukingu	Inclusive model school	2 blind learners 35 with intellectual disabilities 15 with physical disabilities 6 with multiple disabilities	0	1 Perkins braille 1 slate and stylus

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Schools/centres	School type	# of learners/persons with disabilities	Available assistive technology	
			High-tech	Low-tech
EP Gitabi	Mainstream school	8 learners with various disabilities: intellectual disabilities, low vision, speech	0	0
Blessing School for the Visually Impaired (BSVI)	Special school	30 blind learners	10 desktop computers with JAWS screen reader 15 Orbit Readers, 20	21 Perkins brailers
Sunzu Yacu Community Library	Community library	N/A	1 Orbit Reader 20	0
GS Rosa Mystica	Inclusive school	81 learners with hearing, physical, intellectual and multiple disabilities	0	0
Ruhango community library	Community library	N/A	1 Orbit Reader 20	0

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Schools/centres	School type	# of learners/persons with disabilities	Available assistive technology	
			High-tech	Low-tech
EP Bunazi	Mainstream school	6 learners with intellectual disabilities	N/A	0
Educational institute for the Blind Children	Special school	172 blind and low vision learners	20 Orbit Readers 20 25 computers with screen readers 2 Braille embossers	70 Perkins brailers 60 Slates and styluses
HVP Gatagara, Rwamagana	Special school	170 blind and low vision learners	51 Orbit Reader 20	180 Slate and stylus 100 Perkins brailers
Rwamagana Community Library	Community library	0	0	0
GS Rwantonde	Mainstream school	10 learners with intellectual disabilities 7 learners with physical disabilities	0	0

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Schools/centres	School type	# of learners/persons with disabilities	Available assistive technology	
			High-tech	Low-tech
GS Rwisirabo	Inclusive model school	1 blind learner 1 deaf learner 5 learners with intellectual disabilities	1 Orbit Reader 20	1 Perkins braille 1 slate and stylus
Ubumwe Community Centre(UCC)	Inclusive school	28 learners with physical disabilities, 26 with intellectual disabilities, 14 deaf learners, 5 with skin disability, 10 with visual disabilities, 6 with multiple disabilities	4 Orbit Readers 20 1 smart screen	0
EP Muramba A,	Inclusive model school	1 blind learner 8 learners with intellectual disabilities 1 learner with physical disabilities	1 Orbit Reader 20	0

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Schools/centres	School type	# of learners/persons with disabilities	Available assistive technology	
			High-tech	Low-tech
Kabaya Community Library	Community library	N/A	1 Orbit Reader 20	0
GS Gitesi	Inclusive model school	1 learner with hearing disability 7 learners with low vision 4 learners with intellectual disabilities 15 learners with physical disabilities 6 learners with multiple disabilities	0	0

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Schools/centres	School type	# of learners/persons with disabilities	Available assistive technology	
			High-tech	Low-tech
GS Gashashi	Inclusive model school	1 with a hearing disability 4 with low vision 14 learners with intellectual disabilities 2 learners with speech disabilities 4 learners with physical disabilities 3 learners with multiple disabilities	0	0

From the data presented in the table above, it is clear that special schools have more assistive technology in comparison with inclusive model schools and mainstream schools. However, the ratio of assistive devices to learners with disabilities enrolled varies greatly by school. For example, in Blessing School for the visually Impaired, the ratio of Orbit Readers to blind learners enrolled is 1:2, while the ratio is 1:8 in the Educational Institute for the Blind Children and 1:3 in HVP Gatagara, all of which are special schools for blind learners. On the other hand, there are schools that accommodate learners with disabilities but have no assistive technology. These findings indicate that assistive technology were available in some schools and community libraries. However, it was insufficient to cater for the needs of all learners with disabilities.

6.2.2. Availability of UDL-based materials

The study also aimed at finding out the availability of accessible UDL-based materials that teachers used in lessons for learners with disabilities. In all schools, there were limited UDL-informed materials used in lessons, including those made from locally available materials such as bottle tops, bricks, sticks or stones. Digital UDL-based materials were not available at all for learners with disabilities in the schools visited by the research team.

Image 3. UDL-based material made from locally available materials (beans)

Teachers made these materials on their own to provide multiple means of representing knowledge for learners with and without disabilities. These materials were made with the understanding that children's learning styles vary, and that diverse needs must be met. During one FGD with teachers, they mentioned:

“We do an individual education plan (IEP) for each child(with a disability) to set their objectives and make sure they meet those objectives” FGD with teachers in Ubumwe Community Centre.

Some schools also received support from BLF on UDL-based materials to use in teaching learners with and without disabilities. As one teacher from GS Rosa Mystica explained during an FGD:

“ We have materials we were given by BLF which are puzzles you use while teaching about wild animals or domestic animals. We also have number cards in different shapes and rulers. When teaching shapes, you give them to the learners and they feel them. Those are the teaching/learning materials we do have.”
FGD with teachers from Rosa Mystica

Digital UDL-based materials, on the other hand, are not widely available in schools. MINEDUC currently only provides print books to schools. The books are delivered to district offices, which then distribute them to local schools. However, UDL-based materials are rarely made available. One REB official, stated that there is not enough emphasis on making UDL-based materials available:

“For example, the curriculum itself talked about inclusion, and it stated that a teacher must record every child every day including those with disabilities by type of disability in their classroom. But when the CBC was being

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implemented and books were being developed according to the curriculum, they didn't remember this inclusion part...They talk about inclusion, but there is no emphasis when it comes to the implementation”

REB official

Due to the gap in availability of accessible digital UDL-based materials, REB's CTLRD is making an effort to adapt all textbooks for all subjects and make them accessible for learners with disabilities. As the REB official explained:

“We are in the development process working with the curriculum department. We started with eKitabu with one book, and now we have almost 30 accessible books. We need to continue adapting because the adapted books do not cover all lessons.”

REB official

To address the lack of accessible textbooks for learners, some schools have in-house initiatives to transcribe sections of books into braille to support learners with disabilities. In special schools for the blind, textbooks have been embossed in braille and in another case videos were produced in sign language to meet the needs of their learners. The special schools for learners who are blind or partially sighted visited, which were HVP Gatagara, Blessing School for the Visually Impaired and Educational Institute of Blind Children, had transcribed materials from REB to make them accessible for their learners. A teacher at the Educational Institute of Blind Children pointed out:

“The curriculum has some challenges because it is not designed to cater for learners who are blind or partially sighted. Until now, we look for alternative solutions for ourselves to support learners, but there is no common way in which we, teachers, adapt the curriculum.”

During an FGD with teachers at Blessing School for the Visually Impaired, one teacher said:

“We transcribe books ourselves into braille and or we put them in Orbit Readers. It is a challenge.”
FGD with teachers at Blessing School for the Visually Impaired.

Similarly, the resource center that caters for persons with visual disabilities has adapted materials into braille. AS one staff member said:

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“Here at the center, we do our best. We have a braille embosser which helps us to print. We change ordinary text to braille in order to support our trainees. It is challenging because it requires us to rewrite to have it in soft copy, as it is not easy to find soft copies of books.” Masaka Resource Centre

The diagram below illustrates the findings on the types of UDL-based materials used by different learners according to the type of their disability. The diagram also notes observations made in terms of gaps identified in the available UDL-based materials. Overall, UDL-based materials available in schools visited were not designed to incorporate all three main UDL principles, that is, to provide multiple means of engagement, representation, action & expression.

Figure 5. Observations on available UDL-based materials adapted for learners with different disabilities

Disability type	Available UDL-based materials	Observation
Blind	Manipulative locally made materials	Insufficient compared to the number of learners Not standardized Insufficient as braille papers are scarce Do not meet all learning needs of learners
Deaf	Braille print text books transcribed into braille by schools	Available on REB e-learning platform Not compatible with available assistive technology devices Teachers and learners are not aware of this accessible digital text book
Physical	P1 English Accessible Digital Textbook	Available on REB e-learning platform Teachers and learners are not aware of this accessible digital text book Do not meet all learning needs of learners Insufficient compared to the number of learners Not standardized
Intellectual	Visual locally made materials	Insufficient compared to the number of learners Not standardized Do not meet all learning needs of learners
Deaf-blind	Visual locally made materials	Insufficient compared to the number of learners Not standardized Do not meet all learning needs of learners
	Tactile and visual locally made materials	Insufficient compared to the number of learners Not standardized Do not meet all learning needs of learners
	None	No any available UDL-based materials to support their learning process

UDL-based materials for learning developed by the government and other development partners are available on REB's e-learning platform for access by all. However, these are limited and cannot be accessed by all learners with disabilities and their teachers.

6.2.3. Sources of assistive technology and UDL-based materials

OPDs have played a major role in providing access to assistive technology for learners with disabilities. RUB has distributed 75 Orbit Readers 20 to five schools that accommodate learners who are blind. This sourcing initiative has been done through collaboration with REB and other partners.

REB is also augmenting support for learners with disabilities through its inclusive education department, including REB's first ever budgeting for assistive technology and hiring teachers with visual impairments:

“In the ICT department, we have now budgeted for assistive technologies.”

REB Official

GoR is making efforts to create accessible UDL-based materials that will be accessed on e-learning platforms; however, their use in schools has not yet begun. REB also endorsed the use of Orbit Readers in a national launch in 2022 to promote “One Orbit Reader per child with visual disability” and increase the availability of refreshable braille displays in schools.

Development partners have also joined REB in supporting inclusive education with assistive technology and UDL-based teaching and learning materials. With support from All Children Reading (USAID, World Vision and the Australian Government), eKitabu distributed 10 Orbit Reader 20 devices as well as 54 accessible digital supplementary readers developed in USAID Soma Umenye, and 1 accessible English Textbook for P1 developed in UNICEF's Accessible Digital Textbook project. USAID Soma Umenye also supplied 6 Orbit Readers to 6 inclusive and mainstream schools. Further, in order to increase the availability of UDL-based materials, eKitabu and Save the Children, with support from the World Bank REACH Reading Ready project, trained 7 Rwandan publishing houses in how to produce “born accessible” content for use by children with and without disabilities.

6.3. Utilization of assistive technology and UDL-based materials in and out of schools

Image 4. Learners interacting with UDL-based materials on tablets

Assistive technology for education is used to help learners with disabilities to communicate with their peers, teachers, and parents. It also increases a learner's ability to read, write, access and understand written material more easily. UDL based-materials make it easier for learners to participate in class with their peers and teachers.

As indicated by learners from EP Bunazi, a mainstream school:

“We use technology to answer some questions... by using it to read and write.” Learners from EP Bunazi

Some learners in special schools, inclusive model schools and mainstream schools are using assistive technology in learning activities. However, the utilization of assistive technologies and UDL-based materials occurs most in special schools; less in inclusive model schools; and least in mainstream schools.

6.3.1. Utilization of assistive technology and accessible UDL-based materials by learners who are blind

The research found that the utilization of assistive technology by learners with visual impairment in primary school level evolves from lower primary to upper primary level. Learners interviewed in schools for the blind indicated that they started with low tech materials to familiarize themselves with writing and reading in braille.

Learners from Blessing School for the Visually Impaired explained how they use the available assistive technology and how their use evolves as they advance:

Figure 6. Utilization process by blind learners

“In P1, we start by learning how to write using sticks and a board and nails, then continue to slate and stylus. We start using computers and Orbit Readers in P4.”

FGD with learners who are Blind in Blessing School for the Visually Impaired.

As they advance, they get introduced to more advanced assistive technology, such as analog Perkins braille. Once they gain some mastery of these, they start using the Orbit Reader 20 digital

braille devices. Learners with disabilities indicated that their preference in assistive technology was the use of computers with screen readers and Orbit Reader 20 devices, as these have the least limitations and are easy to carry. Learners from HVP Gatagara Rwamagana pointed out:

“The best is a computer with a screen reader, even if we have only a few, but at least computers are more available than other devices.”

FGD with learners from HVP Gatagara Rwamagana

Image 5. Learner with visual impairment using Perkins braille in an inclusive classroom

KII respondents indicated that assistive technology for learners with visual impairments was also used for doing national exams for P6. As a headteacher of a special school for the blind noted:

“We have software that translates normal text into braille, and then we print using the embosser, so it can make many copies of the exam. The only problem we have is to find the papers we need to use for printing. You can’t find them here. Since the children know how to use Orbit Readers, there is also a way we can help them by loading the exam in Orbit Readers. She/he reads and does the exam.”

Headteacher of a special school

UDL-based materials used by learners with visual disabilities that were interviewed were materials transcribed into braille through school-based initiatives. In addition, national exams are provided by REB in braille to meet the needs of blind learners.

However, for textbooks, there are no accessible materials distributed by the Government to schools that cater for the needs of learners with visual impairment. As one DEO pointed out:

“We still need advocacy: the materials that are being distributed are not inclusive. There is a policy for inclusiveness, but it also needs to be facilitated in order to be implemented. We are still receiving materials that are not inclusive.” District official

Learners with visual impairment in special schools had some access to UDL-based materials; learners in inclusive model schools and mainstream schools had no access to these materials.

6.3.2. Utilization of assistive technology and accessible UDL-based materials by learners who are deaf

Figure 7. Common approaches used by learners who are deaf

Learners who are deaf had few types of assistive technologies used in learning. The assistive technology available to them is mainly used in exchange for information that translate other languages into RSL. For example, text highlights that they can read and speech-to-text software for accessing audio materials. The diagram on the left highlights different common approaches and assistive technologies for use by learners who are deaf.

Utilization of assistive technologies for learning in schools that accommodate learners who are deaf starts in primary four. In lower grades, learners use print books and other learning materials. This includes the use of OLPC computers that were distributed to many primary schools. In general, deaf learners in lower grades access lessons through sign language instruction in special schools where teachers have these skills. Learners in GS Institut Filippo Smaldone explained during an FGD:

“Teachers start to teach us how to use computers in P3. When teachers are teaching us in general, they use sign language to help us understand.”

FGD with learners at GS Institut Filippo Smaldone

Accessible UDL-based materials used by learners who are deaf are in digital form, including images and RSL videos. But these materials were only utilized in special schools. Teachers explained in an FGD:

“Yes, mostly the use of images helps and because we have computers and a smart screen board where we can show them videos in sign language, that facilitates us in teaching.”

FGD with teachers at GS Institut Filippo Smaldone

Although some inclusive model schools had received digital supplementary readers with RSL videos, they were not used by learners who are deaf due to the limited skills of teachers and limited devices to access the materials. In mainstream schools, there were no available UDL-based materials for use by learners who are deaf.

6.3.3. Utilization of assistive technology and UDL-based materials by learners with physical disabilities

There was no mention of UDL-based materials that were specifically used by learners with physical disabilities. These learners used the same materials as mainstream learners. The assistive resources used by learners with physical disabilities varied greatly depending on the type and severity of the disability.

In the words of one teacher from Ubumwe Community Centre:

“Assistive technology usage varies based on the severity of the disability. For learners without severe disabilities, digital devices are commonly used. For communication barriers, speech-to-text and text-to-speech technology is employed. For physical difficulties, mobility aids like wheelchairs, walkers, and accessible infrastructure are utilized.”

The training that teachers received did not put emphasis on using assistive technologies by learners with physical disabilities. As one teacher mentioned: “We continued having different trainings, but most of them were on how we can assist children with disabilities. For example, they trained us how to push wheelchairs for children with physical disabilities.” Teacher during FGD at Ubumwe Community Centre

6.3.4. Utilization of assistive technology and UDL-based materials by learners with intellectual disabilities

The research showed that learners with intellectual disabilities did not have access to assistive technology for learning. Teachers reported using alternative methods to support learning, focusing on independence and basic skills. GS Rwisirabo had received an intellectual machine from NUDOR, but it was not functioning. During an FGD, teachers at GS Rwisirabo described the machine as a “small, laptop-like device with games and sound-producing buttons.”

To engage learners with intellectual disabilities, teachers used interactive activities and materials such as balls, drawings, and toys.

6.3.5. Utilization of assistive technology and accessible UDL-based materials by teachers

Teachers in special schools used assistive technologies such as embossers for printing braille materials and screen readers such as JAWS for documents, for curriculum materials and for planning their lessons. They also used smart boards in delivering sign language video lessons. A recent initiative by GoR has brought focus to hiring teachers with visual impairments and providing them with laptops with screen reader software for access to teaching and learning materials.

Image 6. UDL-based materials using locally available objects in a mathematics lesson

This initiative aims to build a more inclusive education system. Meanwhile, teachers in inclusive model schools and mainstream schools infrequently use assistive technologies due to their limited knowledge and limited availability of these tools. However, teachers at HVP Gatagara Rwamagana noted:

“We are comfortable with Victor Readers and Orbit Readers, but some of us don’t know how to use them. It would be better if we had more materials and more training on how to use them. For example, we were trained on us of Orbit Reader, but it would be better if we had them to practice on individually.”
FGD with teachers from HVP Gatagara

It is worth noting that the orbit readers available in schools are used by learners, not teachers.

With regard to the use of UDL-based materials, teachers design materials following the CBC guidelines to address different learning styles. Teachers used different items made from locally available materials such as beans, bottles tops, and sticks to support learners, mostly in mathematics and alphabet lessons.

6.3.6. Utilization of assistive technology and accessible UDL-based materials out of school

Image 7. A community education worker reading with children

The research team visited four community libraries and Kigali Public Library and interviewed the parents of children with disabilities to assess the use of assistive technology outside of school settings. The community libraries provide access to reading materials and enhance literacy. They had received Orbit Readers to assist children with visual impairments with accessing books. Laptops with adapted books and RSL videos were provided for deaf children to improve their literacy skills at the library.

The librarians in these community libraries indicated that the available assistive technologies were not used because children with disabilities do not come to the library. In addition, librarians stated that they lacked the skills and capacity to use the available assistive technology and support children with disabilities who might require accessible supplementary materials.

“We have one Orbit Reader for children with visual impairment, but we have not yet received a person who needs to use it, and we do not know how to use it to support them in case they come.”

Librarian

Parents reported a lack of assistive technology at home due to affordability and lack of knowledge on how to support their children. Most parents were deterred by the perceived high cost of technology. Parents of children with disabilities in Ngororero mentioned:

“Even us parents don’t have skills to help our children. Even if we had computers, we wouldn’t be able to help them.”

FGD with parents of children with disabilities in Ngororero district

Parents lacked knowledge of accessible UDL-based materials and understood them to be those used by teachers to support children with disabilities at school. However, they reported using items such as locally made toys and play materials at home to keep their children active. Parents in Ruhango shared this perspective:

“Sometimes, we use a phone with photos, and we also use books with pictures, and we try to play with him to make him happy and keep him interested. The radio also helps. He uses it during the holidays to learn.”

FGD with parents of children with disabilities in Ruhango district

6.4. Efficacy of assistive technology and UDL-based materials

Assistive technology and UDL-based materials have proven valuable tools for learners with disabilities, as they help to address some of the barriers learners with disabilities face in accessing education. However, the efficacy of assistive technology and UDL-based materials depend on different factors, including the specific technology used and availability of support and training for both learners and teachers. For example, low tech assistive devices for blind learners such as Perkins braille machines are heavy to carry and loud when used during lessons.

The effectiveness of assistive technology in improving the learning outcomes of learners with disabilities can be gauged by its use in accessing learning content; facilitating participation in lessons, assessments, and exams; and enabling engagement in learning. A DEO in charge of nursery, primary, and adult education noted:

“In education, it is important to understand a learner's needs and goals, both in the present and for their future in education. This should go hand in hand with providing the tools and resources necessary to achieve academic success. With the availability of inclusive electronic devices and accessible materials, these learners will be able to reach their full potential and prove that they are not weak learners.”

DEO in charge of nursery, primary, and adult education

In the study, learners in special schools shared how assistive technologies enabled them to access textbook content and learn as their peers do in mainstream schools.

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Assistive technology in schools has helped learners with disabilities to be more independent in accomplishing tasks such as homework and revision of lesson materials. This was expressed by one of the school resource room administrators, who pointed out:

“When people with disabilities are using assistive technology, the result will be the same as those with no disability, so in that case persons with disabilities are fully independent.”

A school resource room administrator

Assistive technology has also enabled children with disabilities to improve their literacy through the availability of supplementary readers in accessible formats distributed to some schools. Teachers from special schools indicated that the use of assistive technology helped them to share lessons easily and make sure learners with disabilities could access the intended learning content directly. Through the use of assistive technology and accessible UDL-based materials, teachers were confident they could improve the performance of their learners with disabilities to reach the same level as the best performing mainstream learners:

“It may also depend on how a teacher prepares lessons using assistive technologies. The result could be positive... to facilitate teaching and learning activities, it may help children to focus more on what they see instead of using sign language that I don't even master well.”

FGD with teachers at GS Institut Filippo Smaldone

The availability of accessible UDL-based learning materials contributes to the effectiveness of assistive technology by providing learners with disabilities access to adapted teaching and learning materials and allowing them to participate in learning activities. Access to materials can be enhanced by redefining policies and incorporating accessibility guidelines into the design of curriculum materials. Respondents felt that existing policies were sufficient but needed to be implemented in an inclusive manner:

“The available policies are good ones, but their implementation is still a problem. It is not done as properly as it should be.”

OPD representative

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MINEDUC also emphasized:

“Maybe no additional legal provisions are needed, but there is a need to strengthen and reinforce the existing legal provisions, so that the implementation is from the papers to practice.”

MINEDUC official

The findings of the research reflect the experiences, views and opinions of the respondents regarding the availability and utilization of assistive technologies and UDL based materials in Rwanda. Respondents highlight the gap that still exists despite the evident efforts made so far. The cross representation of the respondents of learners, teachers and stakeholders give value to the above represented findings.

7. Analysis

7.1. Availability and utilization of assistive technologies and UDL based-materials

7.1.1. Availability

The research found that while assistive technologies and UDL-based materials are available in primary schools, they are insufficient and unevenly distributed across different types of schools. Special schools have the most available assistive technologies, followed by inclusive model schools, while mainstream schools have the least.

The available assistive technologies were categorized as high-tech or low tech, as shown in the table below. The researchers categorized “digital” devices that typically integrate software and hardware as “high-tech.” Traditional “analog” solutions such as Perkins brailers, the slate and stylus and braille boards were generally considered “low tech” by participants in the study.

Table 6. Categorization of available assistive technology by types of disabilities

Disability type	High Tech	Low Tech
Deaf/hard of hearing	Laptop, Tablets, Smart screen boards, Smartphones Software for accessibility: Sign language video, text highlighting, supportive captions, Whatsapp	Phones (KaiOS, feature phones), books with sign language Accessibility feature: Messaging
Blind/low	Orbit Reader 20, Laptops, digital recorders,	Perkins brailers, slate and stylus, magnifiers, white

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Disability type	High Tech	Low Tech
vision	CCTV, reading camera, embossers Software for accessibility: JAWS, NVDA, Talk-back, text to speech	cane, Accessibility features: large print, audio, colors, contrast
Intellectual	Intellective machine Software for accessibility: Speech transformation, text highlight	Printed books Accessibility features: Images, pictures exchanging, colors, contrast
Physical	Electric wheelchairs, mouth stick Software: Speech transformation	Crutches and wheelchairs

During field visits, different types of assistive technology were observed for learner who are blind, but fewer options existed for deaf learners.

Findings show that the available assistive technologies in schools are limited and not enough to meet the needs of learners with disabilities. Efforts have been made to provide assistive technology for learners who are blind, progressing from low tech to high-tech tools as learners' progress, beginning in lower primary grades. However, there are fewer assistive technologies available for learners who are deaf and learners with intellectual disabilities.

The availability of UDL-based materials for learners with disabilities is very limited. Further, the materials that are available are not designed to incorporate all 3 main principles of UDL: provide multiple means of engagement, representation, action and expression. The study found that UDL-based materials in schools were mainly produced through school-based initiatives, particularly in special schools. In inclusive model schools and mainstream schools, the available materials were made from locally available objects. Digital UDL-based materials were not at all available in inclusive model schools and

mainstream schools. The findings indicate that although there is a curriculum for inclusive education and special needs, and CTLRD is in the process of providing 30 digital UDL-based textbooks, there is still a wide gap in the availability of these materials. There are, however, resources available online, including n REB's e-learning platform and the Global Digital Library, that have been specifically designed to be accessible and inclusive for learners with disabilities in Rwanda. These resources are a valuable starting point for creating and using UDL-based materials in primary schools.

7.1.2. Effective utilization

Assistive technologies can improve learning outcomes for learners with disabilities, but due to their limited availability in schools, learners have insufficient access to them. In inclusive model schools, the ratio of assistive devices to learners with disabilities was greater than 1:10. There is no meaningful ratio in mainstream schools, due to the lack of assistive technology and fewer learners with disabilities enrolled in mainstream schools. Notably, in special schools, the utilization of assistive technology with learners in higher grades may limit the amount of time learners have to become comfortable with the technology.

Limited skills of teachers to use assistive technology greatly affect the utilization of assistive devices and accessible materials among learners with disabilities. The findings indicated that the majority of schools have appropriate infrastructure such as electricity, and many have internet connectivity and computers, but fewer had devices and materials that were accessible for learners with disabilities. For example, the One Laptop Per Child devices do not accommodate accessibility software and accessible materials for learners with disabilities.

Materials that reflect UDL concepts and made by teachers from locally available objects were in use, but teachers need to be trained in how to effectively use UDL-based materials in formats that are accessible for learners with disabilities and how to adapt materials to meet the needs of learners with disabilities.

7.2. Training for teachers on use of assistive technology and UDL-based materials

Some teachers have received introductory training in inclusive education and UDL principles, while some special school teachers have received practical training in integrating assistive technology in the classroom. However, many teachers have received only minimal and brief training, with little impact on classroom practices. A significant number of teachers, especially recently hired ones, have not received training in inclusive education, UDL principles, or the use of assistive technology. Although teacher training materials in Kinyarwanda on inclusive education and UDL are available, limited training resources exist on how to use assistive technologies in teaching and learning. Teachers in inclusive and mainstream schools would benefit from training on all of these topics.

7.3. Factors affecting the availability and use of assistive technology and UDL-based materials

The research highlights various factors that impact the availability and utilization of assistive technology, both positive and negative. These factors are elaborated in the table below.

Table 7. Positive and negative factors that impact availability and utilization of assistive technology and UDL-based materials

Positive factors	Negative factors
<p>1. Policy and Government initiatives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Marrakesh Treaty Implementation Roadmap for Rwanda has been validated to increase access to books and literary works in accessible formats for those who are blind, visually impaired, or print-disabled. 	<p>1. Policy implementation</p> <p>The policy lacks provisions for funding assistive technology and UDL-based materials to support the education of learners with disabilities.</p> <p>2. Teacher capacity</p> <p>Limited teacher training results in low capacity to support learners in using available assistive</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Launch of Orbit Reader 20 by REB aiming at ensuring access to educational content and reading materials for learners with visual impairment.● CTRLRD is working on providing accessible textbooks for all CBC subjects.● Rwanda's "Education for All" policy has increased the enrollment of children with disabilities¹⁹, and the Special Needs and Inclusive Education (SNIE) policy focuses on improving their education and access to curriculum materials.● The SNIE policy has ensured a focus on improving the education of children with disabilities and ensuring that they have equal access to curriculum materials.²⁰ <p>2. Teacher capacity</p> <p>TTCs have incorporated inclusive education into their courses, which will help graduate teachers to support learners with disabilities in their classrooms.</p> <p>There are available training modules and guides on REB's e-learning platform that have content to increase the knowledge and skills of teachers on inclusive education, UDL-based materials and assistive technology.²¹</p>	<p>technology and UDL-based materials.</p> <p>3. Cost</p> <p>The high cost of assistive technology and digital UDL materials limits their availability. Hardware and software technologies with accessibility features are more expensive than those needed by mainstream learners.</p> <p>4. Lack of awareness</p> <p>Government representatives, stakeholders, teachers, parents, and learners have limited awareness of the various assistive technologies available for different disabilities, greatly affecting their sourcing.</p> <p>5. Standardization of instructional languages and codes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">● There is no common braille code uses across schools for learners with visual impairment, which affect the availability of UDL-based materials in the county.● There is no unified Kinyarwanda braille code, which makes it difficult to transcribe Kinyarwanda materials in braille●
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¹⁹ Republic of Rwanda, Ministry of Education, Education Sector Policy, 2003

²⁰ Republic of Rwanda, Ministry of Education, Special Needs and Inclusive Education Policy 2018- 2023.

²¹ <https://elearning.ict.e.reb.rw/course/index.php?categoryid=266>

<p>3. Infrastructure</p> <p>There is available infrastructure in schools that supports utilization of assistive technology such as electricity, smart classrooms and availability of internet in some schools.</p> <p>4. Stakeholder engagement</p> <p>A number of interventions have distributed assistive technologies and UDL-based materials to schools with learners with disabilities.</p>	<p>The RSL dictionary is still undergoing an approval process, which impacts availability of appropriate materials for learners who are deaf.</p>
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A number of challenges and barriers were identified which hinder the effective use of assistive technologies and UDL based-materials to support the education of learners with disabilities. These include limited awareness by teachers, parents and other stakeholders about available options related to the use of assistive technologies and UDL based-materials. Existing interventions tend to focus on supplying assistive technology devices and UDL Based-Materials, but not on training the user on how to use the supplied items. Additionally, where training has been provided, it tends to be too brief and therefore ineffective. For assistive technology and UDL-based materials to effectively improve learning outcomes for learners with disabilities, there must be focus on addressing specific barriers in the system faced by learners with disabilities. Tools for accessibility such as screen readers, speech recognition software and accessible learning materials allow persons with disabilities to access and interact with the same knowledge as their non-disabled peers. Consideration should be given to using digital materials such as ebooks, videos, audio, braille and dyslexic friendly text formats as these are more accessible than traditional materials.

8. Recommendations and Conclusion

8.1 Recommendations

Assistive technology can help learners with disabilities, as it can provide them with tools and open up strategies to overcome barriers to success in learning. In addition, UDL-based materials can be accessed and used by learners with diverse abilities and disabilities. In Rwanda, there is growing interest in UDL-based materials and their potential to improve learning outcomes for all learners with and without disabilities. The recommendations below were derived from the feedback of respondents in the study and analysis of data on the availability and utilization of assistive technology and UDL-based materials for learners with disabilities in primary schools.

In order to increase the availability and utilization of assistive technology and UDL-based materials for learners with disabilities in primary level:

1. Start by assessing the needs of learners. Consider the range of learners' abilities and disabilities and where learners are located in the current system of special schools, inclusive model schools and mainstream schools—as well as a large proportion of children with disabilities who are not enrolled in any school.
2. Research assistive technology options according to functionality and cost. Many assistive technologies are available in Rwanda, ranging from low tech to high-tech, including technologies that are increasingly integrated into devices, such as screen readers and speech recognition software.
3. Allocate funding for appropriate assistive technology and coordinate across education sector interventions to avoid duplication of efforts, redundant technology investments and e-waste.
4. Provide training and support to teachers of learners with disabilities. Continuous support is necessary to increase utilization of assistive technology and integrate the use of UDL-based materials in teaching and learning.
5. Sensitize all education stakeholders on the importance of assistive technology and accessibility in teaching and learning materials to advance the learning outcomes of learners with disabilities.
6. Emphasis should be placed on high-tech and affordable assistive technologies, as they are most efficient and promote digital literacy and a learner's independence. An example of such assistive technology is the Orbit reader 20 which was found in most of the schools and libraries which participated in this study.

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Recommendations for MINEDUC and GoR institutions:

1. MINEDUC and REB should promote the use of assistive technology, avail accessible UDL-based materials and encourage their effective use in schools to support learners with disabilities.
2. MINEDUC and NESA should monitor the implementation of the Special Needs and Inclusive Education policy.
3. NCPD should collaborate with Rwanda Revenue Authority to ensure that all assistive devices for education are exempted from taxes to reduce their cost.
4. GoR in collaboration with public and private sector partners should expedite the implementation of the Marrakesh Treaty roadmap to facilitate production of learning materials for learners with visual impairments or print disabilities.
5. MINEDUC, REB and RUB should work with experts to develop a standard Kinyarwanda Braille code.
6. GoR should recognize RSL as a national language.
7. MINEDUC, REB, NCPD and RNUD should finalize the RSL dictionary, recognize RSL as a language of instruction and digitize the RSL dictionary to facilitate access to RSL teaching and learning.
8. MINEDUC and REB should define and implement accessibility standards in procurement of devices and teaching and learning materials for use in Rwandan schools.
9. MINEDUC and REB should seek opportunities to engage and support local private sector publishers in sustainable development of accessible teaching and learning materials in local languages.
10. MINEDUC and partners in education should support teachers of learners with disabilities with training and support in utilization of assistive technology and UDL-based materials.

Recommendations for education stakeholders and OPDs:

1. Advocate with GoR to raise awareness regarding appropriate assistive technologies for learners with disabilities.
2. Leverage existing technology in schools and communities and provide training and support for utilization.
3. Collaborate with OPDs to understand the learning needs of learners with disabilities.
4. Undertake needs assessments and **coordinate** before implementing new interventions with assistive technology and UDL-based materials.

Recommendations for teachers and educators:

1. Use available training modules and guides, including ones that are open source, on inclusive education, assistive technology and UDL-based materials to improve capacity to accommodate learners with disabilities.

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2. Use CPD opportunities to integrate inclusive education principles and practices.
3. Schools with devices or smart classrooms should make sure their devices have in-built or installed accessibility features for learners with disabilities.

8.2 Conclusion

Assistive technology and UDL-based materials are two important components that can help learners with disabilities to access and participate in education and improve their learning outcomes. The findings and recommendations of this study highlight both the lack of assistive technologies and UDL-based materials as well as the lack of capacity of teachers to effectively utilize these tools in teaching and learning—and the importance of assistive technology and UDL-based materials to accommodate the learning needs of learners with disabilities in primary schools. There is a need for the government, teachers, educators, parents and communities to work together to close the gaps in adequate support for learners with disabilities. This includes making sufficient assistive technology and UDL-based materials available, particularly in schools. Taking these actions will improve the learning outcomes of learners with disabilities and make education in Rwanda more inclusive and equitable for all.

9. Annexes

9.1. Annex A. The list of special schools in the country

	Name of institutions	Disability Focus	Location	Special School Vs Centre	Gov Aided Vs Private	Education Provided
1	Blessing School for the Visually Impaired	Blind	Musanze	School	Private	Curriculum Based
2	St Gabriel, Centre des Jeunes Sourds-Muets	Deaf	Huye	School	Gov Aided	Curriculum Based
3	Institut Filippo Smaldone	Deaf	Nyarugenge	School	Gov Aided	Curriculum Based
4	Hirwa Iwanyu	Mental	Nyarugenge	Centre	Private	Basic Education
5	Centre Espoir Umwana Nk'abandi	Mental	Nyarugenge	Centre	Private	Basic Education
6	Centre de jour ' Rera Bose'	Mental	Nyarugenge	Centre	Private	Basic Education
7	Centre de Jour Humura HPV Gatagara	Mental	Gasabo	Centre	Private	Basic Education
8	Centre de Jour Tubiteho	Mental	Gasabo	Centre	Private	Basic Education
9	Jyamubandi Mwana	Mental, Physical	Gasabo	Centre	Private	Basic Education

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	Name of institutions	Disability Focus	Location	Special School Vs Centre	Gov Aided Vs Private	Education Provided
10	Izere Mubyeyi	Mental	Kicukiro	Centre	Private	Basic Education
11	Centre Amizero	Mental	Kicukiro	Centre	Private	Basic Education
12	HVP Gatagara Gikondo	Mental	Kicukiro	Centre	Private	Basic Education
13	Centre INSHUTI ZACU Gahanga	Mental	Kicukiro	Centre	Private	Basic
14	Centre Amizero y'ubuzima	Mental	Gisagara	Centre	Private	Basic
15	Centres des handicapés de Mugombwa	Intellectual, Mental	Gisagara	Centre	Private	Curriculum
16	Educational Institute of Blind of Franciscan Sisters Servants of the Cross	Blind	Nyaruguru	School	Gov Aided	Curriculum
17	GS Rosa Mystica	Multiple	Kamonyi	School	Gov Aided	Curriculum
18	HRD la Misericorde	Intellectual, Mental	Muhanga	Centre	Private	Basic
19	ADAR Tubahoze	Mental	Huye	Centre	Private	Basic
20	HVP Gatagara Nyanza	Physical, Deaf	Nyanza	School	Gov Aided	Curriculum
21	Centre Izere (Babeth Diane)	Multiple	Gicumbi	Centre	Private	Basic
22	Centre Barerwe	Deaf	Musanze	School	Private	Basic
23	Centre of Sisters of St. Vincent de Paul	Mental, Physical	Musanze	Centre	Private	Basic

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	Name of institutions	Disability Focus	Location	Special School Vs Centre	Gov Aided Vs Private	Education Provided
24	GS Rukingu/Maison d'accueil d'esperance	Multiple	Rulindo	School	Gov Aided/public	Curriculum
25	Amis Apax Janja	Physical, Mental	Gakenke	School	Gov Aided	Curriculum
26	HVP Gatagara Rwamagana	Blind	Rwamagana	School	Gov Aided	Curriculum
27	Kayonza School for Deaf-Blind	Deaf Blind	Kayonza	School	Private	Curriculum
28	Urugo Rw'amahoro rwa Bare, Mutendeli	Deaf, Physical	Ngoma	Centre	Private	Basic
29	Centre Wikwiheba	Mental, Multiple	Gatsibo	Centre	Private	Curriculum
30	Umutara Deaf School (UDS)	Deaf	Nyagatare	School	Private	Curriculum
31	AVEH Umurerwa	Mental	Bugesera	Centre	Private	Basic
32	Institut Filippo Smaldone Nyamata	Deaf	Bugesera	School	Gov Aided	Curriculum
33	Centre des handicapés de Nkanka	Mental	Rusizi	Centre	Private	Basic
34	Centre des handicapés de Saint Francois d'Assise	Multiple	Rusizi	Centre	Private	Basic
35	Centre Ngwinondebe Ntendezi	Mental	Nyamasheke	Centre	Private	Curriculum
36	Centre Komera	Mental, Deaf	Rutsiro	School	Gov Aided	Curriculum
37	Ineza Kabaya	Mental	Ngororero	Centre	Private	Curriculum
38	Apax Muramba	Mental, Physical	Ngororero	School	Private	Basic
39	Centre Wibabara	Mental	Ngororero	Centre	Private	Basic

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	Name of institutions	Disability Focus	Location	Special School Vs Centre	Gov Aided Vs Private	Education Provided
40	CENTRE DE JOUR NYANGE/ Day Centre	Multiple	Ngororero	Centre	Private	Basic
41	Ubumwe Community Centre (UCC)	Multiple	Rubavu	School	Private	Curriculum
42	Vision Jeunesse Nouvelle	Deaf	Rubavu	Centre	Private	Basic
43	HVP Gatagara, Huye	Deaf, Physical	Huye	School	Gov Aided	Curriculum
44	HVP Gatagara Ruhango	Multiple	Ruhango	School	Gov Aided	Curriculum
45	Nyabihu Demonstration School for the Deaf	Deaf	Nyabihu	School	Private	Curriculum
46	Masaka Resource Centre	Blind	Kicukiro	Centre	Private	Basic
47	Heroes School	Physical	Kicukiro	School	Private	Curriculum
48	Autisme Rwanda	Autisme	Gasabo	Centre	Private	Basic
49	CEFAPEK	Multiple	Kamonyi	Centre	Private	Basic
50	Deaf People and Training Centre - Wisdom	Deaf	Musanze	Centre	Private	Curriculum

9.2. Annex B. Data Collection Tools

9.2.1. Key Informant Interview Guide for Use with Headteachers

Key area	Domain and dimension	Research questions
Introduction	General	<p>I. What is the enrollment rate of children with disabilities? <i>Abana bafite ubumuga mwakira buri mwaka bari ku kihe kigero ?</i></p> <p>II. Do you know of any policies available in support of inclusive education for children with disabilities? (Special needs education policy, 2018) <i>Hari politiki iriho uzi ishyigikira uburezi budaheza ku bana bafite ubumuga?</i></p> <p>III. How is education for children with disabilities delivered? (Through special schools, through special classes/units in mainstream schools, through resource teachers) <i>Uburezi ku bana bafite ubumuga butangwa bute? (mu mashuri yihariye, mu mashuri ahuriwemo na bese, ndetse n’abarimu bafite ubumenyi ku burezi budaheza)</i></p> <p>IV. What types of learning provisions exist for children with disabilities at your school? (special programmes that exist) <i>Ni izihe gahunda zihari zifasha mu myigire y’abana bafite ubumuga ku kigo cyawe?</i></p> <p>V. Are there guidelines at your school that establish the right of all children to receive a quality education? <i>Ese mu kigo cyanyu hari amabwiriza aha abana bese uburenganzira k’uburezi bufite ireme?</i></p>

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		<p>VI. Is there a need for additional legal provisions to accommodate better learners with disabilities?</p> <p><i>Ese hari andi mategeko ubona akenewe mu korohereza birushijeho imyigire y'abana bafite ubumuga?</i></p>
Reach	Enabling environment	<p>I. What assistive technologies do you know in their learning? (screen readers, magnifiers, Braille displays, large print materials, sign language video, text highlights)</p> <p><i>Ni irihe koranabuhanga nyunganizi uzi rifasha abana bafite ubumuga mu myigire yabo?</i></p> <p>II. Which ones do you know that are used by learners who are blind or have print disability, deaf learners, with intellectual disabilities, or physical?</p> <p><i>Ni izihe uzi zikoreshwa n'abana bafite ubumuga bwo kutabona cyangwa badakoresha inyandiko zisanzwe, ubumuga bwo kutumva, ubumuga bwo mutwe?</i></p> <p>III. Which ones do you have in your school? How many? Who provided them?</p> <p><i>Ni izihe mufite ku kigo cyanyu? Ni bingahe? Ninde wabibahaye?</i></p> <p>IV. How has the use of assistive technology in education evolved over the past years in improving learning outcomes?</p> <p><i>Ni gute ikoreshwa ry'ikoranabuhanga nyunganizi mu burezi bw'abana bafite ubumuga ryagiye ritera imbere mu myaka ishize mu kuzamura umusaruro mu myigire?</i></p> <p>V. In which areas has your school undertaken significant initiatives to advance the use of assistive technologies to include children with disabilities in education in the past years?</p>

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		<p><i>Mu myaka ishize n'ikihe kintu kigaragara ikigo cyanyu cyaba cyarakoze mu guteza imbere ikoranabuhanga nyunganizi mu burezi bw'abana bafite ubumuga?</i></p> <p>VI. Are there infrastructures in place to support the use of assistive technology for learners with disabilities? (e.g. electricity, smart or special classrooms to use them)</p> <p><i>Haba hari ibikorwa remezo bihari byunganira ikoresheya ry'ikoranabuhanga nyunganizi mu burezi bw'abana bafite ubumuga? (amashyamba, ibyumba by' ikoranabuhanga mu burezi kugirango rikoreshe)</i></p> <p>VII. Do you think learners with disabilities often experience greater success when they have access to assistive technologies? How so?</p> <p><i>Utekereza ko ikoresheya ry'ikoranabuhanga mu burezi bw'abana bafite ubumuga rituma batsinda neza amasomo? Mu buhe buryo?</i></p>
	<p>Accessible Learning materials</p>	<p>I. Tell me what you understand about Universal Design for Learning.</p> <p><i>Ese kuri wowe imyigire ibereye buri wese waba wumva isobanuye iki ?</i></p> <p>II. What UDL-based accessible educational materials do you know of? Which ones do you know that are used by your learners with disabilities?</p> <p><i>Ni ibihe bitabo n'imfashanyigisho uzi? Ni ibihe bikoresheya n'abana nafite ubumuga?</i></p> <p>III. How have accessible materials in education evolved over the past years in their use in improving learning outcomes at your school?</p>

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		<p><i>Ni gute ibitabo n'imfashanyigisho by'abafite ubumuga bwateye imbere mu myaka ishize rikoresha mu guteza imbere umusaruro w'imyigire?</i></p> <p>IV. In which areas has your school undertaken significant initiatives to advance the use of accessible materials for the inclusion of children with disabilities in education in the past years?</p> <p><i>Mu myaka ishize n'ikihe kintu kigaragara ikigo cyanyu cyaba cyarakoze mu guteza imbere ikoresha ry'ibitabo n'imfashanyigisho bibereye buri wese mu burezi bw'abana bafite ubumuga?</i></p>
	Capacity	<p>I. Do teachers have enough skill in the use of assistive technology? With the use of UDL-based accessible materials?</p> <p><i>Ese abarimu bafite ubumenyi buhagije mu gukoresha ikoranabuhanga nyunganizi? No gukoresha ibitabo n'imfashanyigisho bibereye buri wese?</i></p> <p>II. Have they received training? Which ones? When? By who?</p> <p><i>Baba barahawe amahugurwa? Ayahe? Ryari? Na nde?</i></p>

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Utilization	Demand and availability	<p>I. How do learners use the assistive technologies? Which ones do you think are used more? What accessible materials do they use more?</p> <p><i>Ni gute iryo koranabuhanga rikoresha neza n'abanyeshuri? Ni irihe ryaba rikoresha cyane? Kubera iki?</i></p> <p>II. What challenges do learners with disabilities face when using them?</p> <p><i>Ni izihe mbogamizi abana bahura nazo iyo bazikoresha?</i></p> <p>III. Are accessible material and assistive technologies well-kept? How?</p> <p><i>Ese ibitabo n'imfashanyigisho n'ikoranabuhanga nyunganizi bikoresha n'abana bafite ubumuga bibikwa mu buryo buboneye?Gute?</i></p>
Impact	Standards, monitoring and quality assurance	<p>I. How have the learning outcomes for children with disabilities evolved over the past years? Has it improved? What are the factors that have led to this change? (Technology, awareness, policy, etc.).</p> <p><i>Ni gute umusaruro mu myigire y'abafite ubumuga bwo kutabona wagiye ugaragara mu myaka ishize? Waba wariyongereye? Ni ibi bikorwa byaba byaratumye haba izo mpinduka? (Ikoranabuhanga, kumenya amakuru , politiki n'ibindi).</i></p>
Recommendation		<p>I. What can you recommend to the government to improve the availability and use of assistive technology and accessible materials? What can you recommend to NGOs, CSOs and partners in education?</p> <p><i>N'iki wasaba leta kugirango haboneke ikoranabuhanga nyunganizi n' ibitabo bibereye buri wese kandi bikoreshe? Naho se wasaba iki imiryango itari iya leta n'abafatany bikorwa</i></p>

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		<i>mu burezi?</i>
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9.2.2. Focus Group Discussion Guide for Use with Teachers

Domain and dimension	Guiding questions
General information	<p>I. Can you tell us about the school? What type of school is it? (inclusive, special, mainstream)?</p> <p><i>Waduha amakuru y'ishuri ryawe? Ni ubuhe bwoko bw'ishuri? (iridaheza? Iryihariye cyangwa irya bose?)</i></p> <p>II. What type of learners with disabilities does your school admit?</p> <p><i>Ishuri ryanyu ryakira abana bafite ubuhe bumuga?</i></p> <p>III. How are learners with disabilities facilitated in their learning?</p> <p><i>Abana bafite ubumuga bafashwa bate mu myigire yabo?</i></p> <p>IV. How has the education of learners with disabilities evolved since school started?</p> <p><i>Kuva ishuri ryatangira, ni gute uburezi bw'abana bafite ubumuga bwagiye butera imbere?</i></p>
Capacity development	<p>I. What training and skills have you received on special needs and inclusive education?</p> <p><i>Ni ayahe mahugurwa cyangwa ubumenyi wabonye ku burezi budakomeye?</i></p> <p>II. Have you been trained on using UDL principles in the teaching approach? If so, how?</p> <p><i>Waba warahuguwe ku mahame y'imyigire ibereye buri wese (UDL)? Niba igisubizo ari yego; gute?</i></p> <p>III. Have you received any additional training on the use of assistive technologies? By who? What assistive technologies were you trained about?</p>

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	<p><i>Waba warabonye amahugurwa y'inyongera mw'ikoreshwa ry'ikoranabuhanga nyunganizi? Na nde? Ni irihe koranabuhanga nyunganizi mwahuguweho?</i></p> <p>IV. Were the training provided sufficient and relevant?</p> <p><i>Ese amahugurwa mwahawe arahagije kandi yarakenewe?</i></p> <p>V. What else do you think is needed to improve your skills?</p> <p><i>Ni iki kindi utekereza ko cyazamurira ubumenyi bwawe?</i></p>
Process	<p>I. Does the available curriculum facilitate you to teach learners with disabilities?</p> <p><i>Imfashanyigisho mukoresha yaba ikorohereza kwigisha abanyeshuri bafite ubumuga?</i></p> <p>II. During lesson preparation and delivery, do you consider learners with disabilities? How?</p> <p><i>Ese iyo utegura cyangwa unatanga amasomo yawe waba wita ku bana bafite ubumuga? Mu buhe buryo?</i></p> <p>III. Do the learners with disabilities you teach feel comfortable using assistive technologies in learning? Why? Why not? How do you measure the comfort level?</p> <p><i>Ese abanyeshuri bafite ubumuga wigisha bumva borohewe no gukoresha ikoranabuhanga nyunganizi? Kubera iki? Upima ute urugero rw'ubworohe?</i></p> <p>IV. Do you feel comfortable when supporting learners with disabilities in using assistive technologies?</p> <p><i>Wumva bikorohereza gufasha abanyeshuri bawe bafite ubumuga mu gukoresha ikoranabuhanga nyunganizi?</i></p> <p>V. Do you have enough resources to help you teach using assistive technologies? If not, what</p>

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	<p>other resources do you need?</p> <p><i>Ufite ibikenewe bihagije bigufasha kwigisha ikorehwa ry'ikoranabuhanga nyunganizi? Niba atari ko bimeze, ibindi ukeneye byaba ari ibihe?</i></p>
<p>Accessible Materials</p>	<p>I. Which accessible UDL-based teaching and learning materials principles are available at your school?</p> <p><i>Ku ishuri ryanyu ni izihe mfashanyigisho mufite zikoze hakurikijwe amahame y'imyigire ibereye buri wese (UDL)?</i></p> <p>II. Have you received training on how to use these accessible teaching and learning materials?</p> <p><i>Waba warabonye amahugurwa ku buryo bwo gukoresha izi imfashanyigisho zidaheza mu myigire n'imyigishirize?</i></p> <p>III. What challenges do you encounter in the use of accessible teaching and learning materials for children with disabilities?</p> <p><i>Ni izihe mbogamizi wahuye nazo 'mw'ikorehwa 'ry'imfashanyigisho n'ibikoreho bidaheza mu myigishirize y'abana bafite ubumuga?</i></p>
<p>Impact</p>	<p>I. What are the benefits of using assistive technologies for learners with disabilities?</p> <p><i>Ni akahe kamaro kari mu gukoresha ikoranabuhanga nyunganizi ku banyeshuri bafite ubumuga?</i></p> <p>II. Do you think assistive technologies have any negative learning outcomes for learners with disabilities? Explain?</p>

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	<p><i>Utekereza ko haba hari ingaruka(mbi) zaterwa n'ikoreshwa ry'ikoranabuhanga nyunganizi mu myigire y'abanyeshuri bafite ubumuga? Sobanura.</i></p>
Recommendation	<p>III. What would you recommend to improve special needs and inclusive education and the use of assistive technologies for learners with disabilities?</p> <p><i>Watanga iyihe nama mu kuzamura uburezi budaheza no gukoresha ikoranabuhanga nyunganizi ku banyeshuri bafite ubumuga?</i></p>

9.2.3. Focus Group Discussion Guide for Use with Learners with Disabilities from P2-P6

Domain and Dimension	Questions
General knowledge	<p>I. What materials do you use to read and write in class? Slate and stylers, computers/tablets)?</p> <p><i>Ni ibihe bikoresho bigufasha gusoma no kwandika mu ishuri?</i></p>
Availability and access	<p>I. Currently, in your school, do you use any assistive technology? If yes, which ones? (magnifiers, Braille displays, screen reading software, large print).</p> <p><i>Ubu mu kigo wigamo hari ikoranabuhanga nyunganizi wifashisha? Niba igisubizo ari yego, ni irihe mukoresha?</i></p> <p>II. What are the assistive technologies you mentioned used for? Reading? Writing? Others?</p> <p><i>Ese ikoranabuhanga nyunganizi muvuze rikoreshwa mu gukora iki? mu gusoma? Kwandika? Ibindi?</i></p> <p>III. Do all learners with disabilities who need assistive technology get to use them? Who uses them and why?</p> <p><i>Ese abanyeshuri bafite ubumuga bose bakenera ikoranabuhanga nyunganizi babasha kurikoresha? Ese ni bande barikoresha? Kubera iki?</i></p> <p>IV. When and how did you learn to use assistive technology?</p> <p><i>Ni ryari, ni gute wize gukoresha ikoranabuhanga nyunganizi?</i></p> <p>V. Which one of those is best for you to use and why?</p> <p><i>Ni irihe koranabuhanga nyunganizi rikubereye mu gukoresha, kubera iki?</i></p>

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	<p>VI. Do you have access to similar assistive technologies when you are not in school? Where and how?</p> <p><i>Ese ubasha gukoresha ikoranabuhanga nyunganizi igihe utari ku ishuri? Hehe kandi gute?</i></p>
Challenges and barriers	<p>I. What challenges do you face while using assistive technologies?</p> <p><i>Ni izihe mbogamizi uhura nazo mu gukoresha ikoranabuhanga nyunganizi?(battery/power, locked up, not enough, etc.)</i></p> <p>II. When you need help in using assistive technologies, is your teacher able to support you?</p> <p><i>Iyo ukeneye ubufasha mu gukoresha ikoranabuhanga nyunganizi, ese mwarimu wawe abasha kugufasha?</i></p> <p>III. Does your teacher teach in a way that allows you to learn well? How?</p> <p><i>Ese mwarimu wawe yigisha mu buryo bugufasha kwiga neza? Gute?</i></p> <p>IV. Do you prefer to learn in a classroom where all learners have similar disabilities to yours? Or do you prefer to be in a classroom where there are learners with and without disabilities?</p> <p><i>Ese wahitamo kwigana n'abanyeshuri bafite ubumuga nk'ubwawe? Cyangwa wahitamo kwiga mw'ishuri ririmo abafite ubumuga n'abatabufite?</i></p> <p>V. Do you get support from the teachers and other learners, or do you feel like you miss out on certain parts of the lesson?</p> <p><i>Ese ubona ubufasha bw'abarimu cyangwa abandi banyeshuri cyangwa wumva hari ibice by'isomo bigucika?</i></p>
Impact	<p>I. Are you satisfied with the current assistive technologies that you are using in class?</p>

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	<p>How have they helped you in your learning process?</p> <p><i>Wumva wishimiye ikoranabuhanga nyunganizi ukoresha ubu mw'ishuri? Ubona iryo koranabuhanga ryaragufashije iki mu myigire yawe?</i></p> <p>II. If you are dissatisfied with the assistive technologies, what is the reason? (Too hard to use, always have to share, never has power, doesn't help me personally—I would prefer to use...)</p> <p><i>Niba utishimiye n'iryo koranabuhanga nyunganizi, ni ukubera iki? (riragoye gukoresha, kuritizanya iteka, nta na rimwe rigira umuriro, ntabwo jye rimfasha rwose.....Nahitamo gukoresha.....)</i></p>
Gender	<p>I. Do boys and girls with disabilities have the same access to assistive technology at school?</p> <p><i>Ese abahungu n'abakobwa bagerwaho n'ikoranabuhanga nyunganizi kimwe?</i></p>
Safety	<p>I. Are accessible material and assistive technologies that you use well-kept? How?</p> <p><i>Ese ibitabo n'imfashanyigisho n'ikoranabuhanga nyunganizi bikoreshwa n'abana bafite ubumuga bibikwa mu buryo buboneye?Gute?</i></p>

9.2.4. Key Informant Interview Guide for Use with Organizations of Persons with Disabilities

Key area	Domain and dimension	Research questions
Introduction	General	<p>I. How is the education of children with disabilities in Rwanda? <i>Uburezi bw'abana bafite ubumuga mu Rwanda ububona ute?</i></p> <p>II. How does your organization support the education of children with disabilities? <i>Ese umuryango wanyu ufasha ute imyigire y'abana bafite ubumuga?</i></p> <p>III. Currently, what types of learning provisions exist for children with disabilities? (programmes) <i>Ni ibiki biteganyijwe mu myigire y'abana bafite ubumuga?</i></p> <p>IV. Are there policies and guidelines in place to support education for learners with disabilities? <i>Ese haba hari politiki n'amabwiriza ngenderwaho mu gufasha imyigire y'abana bafite ubumuga</i></p> <p>V. Is there a need for additional legal provisions to better accommodate learners with disabilities? <i>Ese hari andi mategeko akenewe mu korohereza birushijeho imyigire y'abana bafite ubumuga?</i></p>

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<p>Reach</p>	<p>Enabling environment</p>	<p>I. Which assistive technologies do you know that are used by learners who are blind or have print disability? For deaf, for those with intellectual disabilities?</p> <p><i>Ni irihe koranabuhanga nyunganizi uzi rikoreshwa n'abana bafite ubumuga bwo kutabona, kutumva n'ubwo mu mutwe?</i></p> <p>II. How has the use of assistive technology in education evolved over the past years?</p> <p><i>Ni gute ikoreshwa ry'ikoranabuhanga nyunganiz mu burezi bw'abana bafite ubumuga ryagiye ritera imbere mu myaka ishize?</i></p> <p>III. Are there infrastructures in place for assistive technology to be provided to learners with disabilities? (e.g. electricity, smart or special classrooms to use them)</p> <p><i>Hari ibikorwa remezo bihari bifasha ikoreshwa ry'ikoranabuhanga nyunganizi mu burezi bw'abanyeshuri? (amashanyarazi, ibyumba byagenewe ikoranabuhanga mu burezi kugirango rikoreshwe)</i></p> <p>IV. Do you think learners with disabilities often experience greater success when they have access to assistive technologies? How so?</p> <p><i>Utekereza ko ikoreshwa ry'ikoranabuhanga nyunganizi mu burezi bw'abana bafite ubumuga rituma batsinda neza amasomo? Wabisobanura ute?</i></p>
	<p>Learning materials</p>	<p>I. What do you know about Universal Design for Learning (UDL)?</p> <p><i>Ese waba uzi ibijyanye n'uburezi bubereye buri wese (UDL)?</i></p> <p>II. Which UDL-based accessible materials do you know that are used by learners with disability? (e.g. materials that have audio features, image descriptions, e-braille materials)</p>

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		<p><i>Ni izihe mfashanyigisho zibereye buri wese uzi zikoreshwa n'abana bafute ubumuga? (urugero: uburyo bukoresha amajwi, amashusho cyangwa braille).</i></p> <p>III. How has UDL-based accessible materials evolved in education over the past years?</p> <p><i>Ni gute imfashanyigisho ribereye buri wese ryagiye ritera imbere?</i></p> <p>IV. Are there local guidelines on developing accessible materials in education to support learning outcomes?</p> <p><i>Haba hari amabwiriza ajyanye n'itegurwa ry'imfashanyigisho ribereye buri wese?</i></p>
	Availability and utilisation	<p>I. Is there data on all available assistive technologies and accessible materials in your organization?</p> <p><i>Haba hari imibare ku bikoresho by'ikoranabuhanga bisha abana bafite ubumuga mu muryango wanyu?</i></p>
	Capacity	<p>I. Does your organization contribute to improving the capacity of teachers who support learners with disabilities? How?</p> <p><i>Ese umuryango wanyu ugira uruhare mu kuzamura ubumenyi bw'abarimu bafasha abanyeshuri bafite ubumuga?</i></p> <p>II. How about training them on how to use assistive technologies?</p> <p><i>Naho se kubahugura mu ikoresha ry'ikoranabuhanga nyunganizi?</i></p>

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	Funding and resources	<p>I. Does your organization provide assistive technologies and UDL-based accessible materials or funds to support education for learners with disabilities?</p> <p><i>Ese umuryango wanyu utanga ikoranabuhanga nyunganizi n'imfashanyigisho ribereye buri wese cyangwa amafaranga mu gufasha imyigire y'abana bafite ubumuga?</i></p>
	Awareness, attitude	<p>I. Are the schools, teachers, parents and learners aware of the available assistive technologies and UDL-based materials that can support learners with visual impairment in their learning?</p> <p><i>Ese ubona amashuri, abarimu, ababyeyi n'abanyeshuri bazi ko hari ikoranabuhanga nyunganizi n'imfashanyigisho ribereye buri wese zikoreshwa mu myigire y'abana bafite ubumuga?</i></p>
Cross-cutting issues	Gender	<p>I. How does inclusive education address gender-specific needs?</p> <p><i>Ni gute uburezi budaheza bukemura ibibazo by'abana b'abakobwa bafite ubumuga?</i></p> <p>II. Do girls and boys with disabilities have equal access to assistive technologies?</p> <p><i>Ese abakobwa n'abahungu bagera ku buryo bungana kw'ikoranabuhanga rifasha abafite ubumuga?</i></p>
	Social protection	<p>I. Are children with disabilities from poor families supported in accessing inclusive learning? Is there financial support provided to them by your organization?</p> <p><i>Ese abana bafite ubumuga bava mu miryango ikennye bahabwa ubufasha mu myigire yabo? Ese umuryango wanyu waba ubaha inkunga?</i></p>
Recommendation		<p>I. What would you recommend to be improved to support learners with disabilities?</p> <p><i>Ni iki wumva cyakorwa mu kuzamura ubufasha ku bana bafite ubumuga?</i></p>

9.2.5. School Observation Guide

#	Questions	Observations
1	What type of school/institution is it?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mainstream school • Inclusive model school • Special school • Library • Other
2	Is the school accessible?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accessible environment (pathways, toilets) • Classroom • Classroom arrangements
3	Are there supportive infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Electricity • Internet • storages
4	Is there a smart classroom/resource	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, both • No
5	What devices are in the smart classroom?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Laptops • Tablets
6	Accommodation style	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Day • Boarding • Both
7	Number of all learners with and without disabilities in the primary school level?	P1(B/G) P2(B/G) P3(B/G) P4(B/G) P5(B/G) P6(B/G) other(B/G)
8	How many teachers are available? (ask for records)	Numbers....male vs female...any teachers with disabilities?

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9	Are there focal teachers in charge of inclusive education?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes = how many • No
10	Have the teachers been trained in inclusive education?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes = which trainings?..... • No
11	Classroom observation; teacher-learner interaction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learners with disabilities participating in classroom • Learners with disabilities participating in school activities
12	There are learning materials that are used in school. Name them	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Braille papers • Audio • Digital • Print books • Others
13	What assistive technologies are available? Indicate their category (low tech, high tech, reading, writing, audio, printing etc	List.....Category...
14	Which ones are used?	List.....
15	Which ones are not used?	List.....
16	Is there a repair service available to repair devices when not functioning	

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